

1 **Results of a Geant4 benchmarking study for bio-medical**
2 **applications, performed with the G4-Med system,**
3 **developed by the Geant4 Medical Simulation**
4 **Benchmarking Group**

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50 Version typeset June 20, 2024

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53 Abstract

54 **Background:** Geant4, a Monte Carlo Simulation Toolkit extensively used in bio-
55 medical physics, is in continuous evolution to respond to the evolving needs of a very
56 diverse user community. In 2014 the G4-Med benchmarking system was born from
57 the effort of the Geant4 Medical Simulation Benchmarking Group, to benchmark and
58 monitor the evolution of Geant4 for medical physics applications. The G4-Med system
59 was first described in Arce et al.¹. Results of the tests were reported for Geant4 10.5.

60 **Purpose:** In this work, we describe the evolution of the G4-Med system since our first
61 publication, in terms of new tests, results of regression testing between Geant4 10.5
62 and 11.1, and the benchmarking of Geant4 electromagnetic physics (EM) constructors
63 and physics lists (including both EM and hadronic physics processes) in terms of execution
64 times.

65 **Methods:** The G4-Med benchmarking suite currently includes 23 tests, which bench-
66 mark Geant4 from the calculation of basic physical quantities to the simulation of more
67 realistic set-ups. New tests concern the benchmarking of Geant4-DNA physics and
68 chemistry components for regression testing purposes, dosimetry for brachytherapy
69 with a ¹²⁵I source, dosimetry for external X-ray and electron FLASH radiotherapy,
70 experimental microdosimetry for proton therapy and in-vivo PET for carbon and oxy-
71 gen beams. Regression testing has been performed between Geant4 10.5 and 11.1.
72 Finally, a simple Geant4 simulation has been developed and used to compare Geant4
73 EM physics constructors and physics lists in terms of execution times.

74 **Results:** In summary, based on the results of our tests, we recommend to use *Opt4*
75 as EM constructor and *QGSP_BIC_HP*, coupled with *Opt4*, for hadronic applications.
76 The Geant4-DNA physics lists report differences in modelling electron interactions in
77 water, however, the tests have a pure regression testing purpose so no recommendation
78 can be formulated.

79 **Conclusions:** The G4-Med benchmarking system proved to be a very powerful tool
80 to monitor the evolution of Geant4 for bio-medical physics applications. Neverthe-
81 less, the development of this tool is not complete yet. Future work will include the

82 full automatisation of the G4-Med system from the execution in geant-val (already
83 automatised) to the inclusion of the results in the geant-val web interface and the
84 analysis of the results (which are currently partially manual). This development will
85 allow to speed-up the G4-Med system when monitoring the evolution of the Geant4
86 physics lists. New tests should be included in the G4-Med suite to cover more Geant4
87 application scenarios in medical physics, for example to benchmark radioactivity, neu-
88 tron production and interactions.

89

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1. Introduction

Geant4 (Agostinelli et al.², Allison et al.^{3,4}) is an open source Monte Carlo Simulation Toolkit modelling particle interactions and transport in matter. Geant4 has undergone continuous development and enhancement since it was initially made available to the public in 1998. These improvements have expanded the software’s functionality and allowed it to better meet the evolving needs of its diverse user community, which includes researchers in fields such as high-energy physics, space, nuclear and bio-medical sciences. The software is developed by an international scientific Collaboration, based at CERN, Geneva, Switzerland, counting more than 100 contributors worldwide. The Monte Carlo code is released with a new public version every year in December. Prior to this, a beta version is usually released in June, and subsequent patches may be issued to fix errors.

As shown in Figure 1, since its first release, Geant4 has become increasingly popular in the bio-medical physics community. Given its extensive use in the scientific community and its wide set of physics models offered to describe both electromagnetic and hadronic physics interactions, in 2014 G4-Med, the first Geant4 benchmarking system for bio-medical physics applications was established. It was born as an effort of the Geant4 Medical Simulation Group Group⁵ to benchmark different physics models of Geant4 in a set of exemplary bio-medical application scenarios of interest.

This international effort was documented for the first time in Arce et al.¹. The tests, ranging from fundamental physical quantities to more realistic applications, were developed and executed with Geant4 10.5 on the CERN computing infrastructure, via the *geant-val* system^{14,15}.

In this paper, we document the evolution of the G4-Med benchmarking system in terms of new tests that have been included and tests that have been revised. We then report significant results of the regression tests performed with Geant4 versions 10.5 and 11.1 (released in December 2022), which was the most recent release of Geant4 when the study described in this paper was started. Finally, we document for the first time the benchmarking of the execution times of the G4-Med tests when using different Geant4 physics lists and constructors. The latter is a critical information in those Geant4-based studies where the computing performance is an important factor.

Figure 1: Number of scientific publications in bio-medical physics, found in the PubMed Central[®] ⁶ archive, searching the general purpose Monte Carlo codes Geant4 (Agostinelli et al.², Allison et al.³ and Allison et al.⁴), FLUKA (Ferrari et al.⁷, Battistoni et al.⁸, Ahdida et al.⁹), MCNP (Goorley et al.¹⁰) and EGSnrc (Kawrakow et al.¹¹ and Kawrakow and Rogers¹²) in keywords, titles and citations of papers recorded in the PubMed archive. The figure contains data (up to 2018) published in Mancini-Terracciano et al.¹³, Copyright Elsevier (2019).

184 II. Methodology

185 The G4-Med benchmarking system, documented for the first time in Arce et al.¹, currently
 186 includes 23 tests, listed in Table 1 and covers different bio-medical application scenarios of
 187 interest. The tests are designed to benchmark Geant4 from the calculation of fundamental
 188 physical quantities to the simulation of more realistic set-ups in medical imaging and radio-
 189 therapy. The tests in the Table are categorised according to the specific physics models and
 190 interactions being tested. These categories include Geant4-DNA tests (Section III.), electro-
 191 magnetic physics tests (Section IV.), tests for hadronic nuclear cross sections (Section V.),
 192 and tests for both electromagnetic and hadronic physics (Section VI.).

193 The *Microdosimetry* test (*microyz*) and *Dose Point Kernel (LowEElectDPK)*, described
 194 in Arce et al.¹, have been adapted to benchmark Geant4-DNA physics lists, while the *Chem-*
 195 *istry* test (*chem6*) has been introduced to benchmark different Geant4 models to describe
 196 the chemical stage of particle interactions in water.

197 New tests have been included to benchmark Geant4 for dosimetric calculations in water
 198 phantoms, for brachytherapy with an ¹²⁵I source (*Brachy* test), external MV X-ray radio-
 199 therapy (*medical_linac* test), and electron FLASH radiotherapy (*eFLASH_radiotherapy* test).
 200 A new hadronic physics test benchmarks Geant4 for in-vivo Positron Emission Tomography

201 (PET) for carbon ion therapy (*heavy-ion-therapy* test), while the *Hadrontherapy* test, origi-
202 nally developed for the calculation of cell survival curves irradiated with a 62 MeV Spread
203 Out Bragg Peak proton beam, has been extended to benchmark the track-averaged LET
204 against experimental measurements (Petringa et al. [16](#)).

205 The G4-Med benchmarking system runs all its tests in the *geant-val* environment [14,15](#).
206 The *chemistry* test is executed on the computing facility of the Laboratoire de Physique des
207 Deux Infinis Bordeaux (LP2IB), while the other tests are executed on the CERN computing
208 infrastructure. Tests can be executed whenever it is necessary to verify the functionality of
209 Geant4 and support the development of Geant4 for bio-medical physics applications.

210 The tests are summarised in the website dedicated to the project Group [5](#), while the
211 simulation results documented in this paper can be downloaded from the *geant-val* web
212 interface [bib](#) [15](#).

Test	Name in <i>geant-val</i> interface ¹⁵	Source	Section
Geant4-DNA tests			
Low energy electron Dose Point Kernels	<i>LowEElectDPK</i>	**	III.C.
Microdosimetry	<i>microyz</i>	*** Kyriakou et al. ¹⁷	III.D.
Chemistry	<i>chem6</i>	**	III.E.
Electromagnetic physics tests			
Brachytherapy - ¹⁹² Ir source	<i>Brachy</i>	***	IV.
Brachytherapy - ¹²⁵I source	<i>Brachy</i>	***	IV.B.
MV x-ray radiotherapy	<i>medical.linac</i>	***	IV.C.
Electron FLASH radiotherapy	<i>eFLASH.radiotherapy</i>	***	IV.D.
Photon attenuation	<i>PhotonAttenuation</i>	Amako et al. ¹⁸	IV.
Electron electronic stopping power	<i>ElectDEDX</i>		IV.
Electron backscattering	<i>ElectBackScat</i>	Dondero et al. ¹⁹	IV.E.1.
13 MeV electron forward scatter from foils	<i>ElecForwScat</i>	Faddegon et al. ²⁰	IV.E.2.
Bremsstrahlung from thick targets	<i>Bremsstrahlung</i>	Faddegon et al. ²¹	IV.E.3.
Fano Cavity	<i>FanoCavity</i>	**	IV.E.4.
Monoenergetic x-ray internal breast dosimetry	<i>Mammo</i>	Fedon et al. ^{22, 23}	IV.
Hadronic nuclear cross section tests			
Nucleus-Nucleus hadronic inelastic scattering cross sections	<i>NucNucInelXS</i>		V.A.1.
62 MeV/u ¹² C fragmentation	<i>LowEC12Frag</i>	Mancini-Terracciano et al. ²⁴	V.A.2.
Charge-changing cross section for 300 MeV/u carbon ions	<i>C12FragCC</i>	Toshito et al. ²⁵	V.A.3.
Electromagnetic and hadronic physics tests			
62 MeV proton beam test: cell survival modelling and track-averaged LET	<i>Hadrontherapy</i>	***, Petringa et al. ^{16, 26}	VI.B.
In-vivo PET for carbon ion therapy	<i>heavy-ion.therapy</i>	Chacon et al. ²⁷ , Chacon et al. ²⁸	VI.C.
67.5 MeV proton Bragg curves in water	<i>LowEProtonBraggBeak</i>	Faddegon et al. ²⁹	VI.D.1.
Light ion Bragg Peak curves	<i>LightIonBraggPeak</i>		VI.D.2.
Neutron yield of protons with energy 113 MeV and 256 MeV and 290 MeV/u carbon ions	<i>ProtonC12NeutronYield</i>		VI.D.3.
Fragmentation of a 400 MeV/u ¹² C ion beam in water	<i>FragTest</i>	Bolst et al. ³⁰	VI.D.4.

Table 1: Tests of *G4-Med* with their name in the *geant-val* interface and the subsections of this report with their description and results. New tests (introduced in the G4-Med benchmarking suite since 2021) are in bold. All the other tests have been documented in detail in Arce et al.³¹. **: tests released as Geant4 *extended* examples; ***: tests released as Geant4 *advanced* examples. The Geant4-DNA and Fano cavity tests have a purely regression testing purpose.

213 II.A. Regression testing

214 Regression testing between Geant4 versions 10.5 and 11.1 is performed to benchmark how
 215 the evolution of Geant4 and its physics capability affects the results of the G4-Med tests.
 216 The tests are executed through *geant-val* with the two different Geant4 versions, using the
 217 same simulation configuration and user-defined physics parameters (for example, *cut* and
 218 *maximum step*). The results of the Geant4 regression testing are analysed by comparing
 219 them with reference data using the methods described below.

220 The ratio r of the simulation results S , obtained with Geant4 10.5 or 11.1, and the
 221 reference data R , i.e. $r_{10.5} = \frac{S_{10.5}}{R}$ and $r_{11.1} = \frac{S_{11.1}}{R}$, are estimated and compared for each point
 222 of the distribution of interest, subject of the comparison. If there is a small misalignment
 223 along the x-axis in the points at which the simulated and reference data points are evaluated,
 224 the closest simulated data point is taken in the computation of the ratio. The uncertainty
 225 affecting the ratios, $\Delta r_{10.5}$ and $\Delta r_{11.1}$, is calculated by direct error propagation as shown in
 226 Equation 1. The difference between $r_{10.5}$ and $r_{11.1}$ is deemed significant when it is greater
 227 than $\Delta r_{\text{version}}$,

$$228 \quad \Delta r_{\text{version}} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta S_{\text{version}}}{S_{\text{version}}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta R}{R}\right)^2} \cdot r_{\text{version}} \quad (1)$$

229 where “version” stands for either Geant4 10.5 or 11.1, $\Delta S_{\text{version}}$ is the statistical uncertainty
 230 of the simulation results and ΔR is the uncertainty affecting the reference data. When
 231 the difference in terms of ratios is deemed significant, the mean relative error (MRE), the
 232 normalised mean absolute error (NMAE) and the maximum difference (MD) between the
 233 simulation and reference data are estimated.

234 MRE is calculated as follows:

$$235 \quad \text{MRE} = \frac{1}{n} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|S_i - R_i|}{R_i} \right] \quad (2)$$

236 where S_i and R_i are the individual data points of the simulation results and reference
 237 data, respectively.

238 The normalised mean absolute error (NMAE) as defined in Equation 3 is also considered
 239 to describe the absolute deviation of simulations to the reference data.

$$\text{NMAE} \equiv \frac{\frac{1}{n} \sum_i |S_i - R_i|}{\frac{1}{n} \sum_i R_i} = \frac{\sum_i |S_i - R_i|}{\sum_i R_i} \quad (3)$$

To complete the analysis, the MD between the simulation and the reference data, as shown in Equation 4, is calculated for each Geant4 release under study to demonstrate the most extreme differences from the experimental data.

$$\text{MD} = \max |S_i - R_i| . \quad (4)$$

Regression testing results are reported and commented on in this article only when there are differences between Geant4 releases 10.5 and 11.1. Nevertheless, the complete data analysis performed in this work can be accessed through the G4-Med analysis website³².

II.B. Computing performance

An important consideration when choosing a Geant4 physics list or constructor for a specific simulation scenario is first the accuracy of results, and then the execution time. If a physics list is more accurate than another, compared to reference/experimental data, but significantly more computationally intensive, then the user may need to decide whether the added accuracy is required or if the added computing resources are justifiable.

The aim of this part of the project, documented in Section VII., is to benchmark the execution times of the Geant4 physics constructors and lists under testing in the G4-Med suite using a simple Geant4 simulation application.

III. Geant4-DNA benchmarking tests

The Geant4-DNA package is extensively used in radiobiological studies; therefore, we felt the need to include new tests in the G4-Med benchmarking suite, to monitor the evolution of Geant4-DNA physics, physico-chemical and chemical stage simulation capabilities. So far, we have included three tests to benchmark Geant4-DNA physics (*microdosimetry* test and *LowEElectDPK*) and the physico-chemical / chemical stages of particle interactions in the *Chemistry* (*chem6*) test.

264 III.A. Geant4–DNA physics constructors

265 The Geant4–DNA extension of Geant4 has been providing a range of processes and physical
266 models since 2007. It focuses on simulating particle interactions with liquid water, which
267 is the primary component of the biological environment. This is particularly relevant for
268 studying the impact of ionising radiation on biological targets at the DNA level Incerti
269 et al.^{33, 34}, Bernal et al.³⁵, Incerti et al.³⁶, Kyriakou et al.³⁷. These processes and models
270 apply to electrons, protons, neutral hydrogen atoms, helium nuclei, and their charge states,
271 as well as to a number of incident ions.

272 The processes to which electrons are subjected in the energy range associated to bio-
273 medical physics applications include ionisation, electronic excitation, vibrational excitation,
274 elastic scattering, and dissociative electron attachment. For protons, neutral hydrogen
275 atoms, helium nuclei, and their charge states, ionisation, electron excitation and elastic
276 scattering are available. For ions heavier than helium, only ionisation is currently taken into
277 account. These processes are described by alternative models, following different approaches
278 (theoretical, semi-empirical) and covering different energy domains. They are either analyt-
279 ically coded or can use cross-section interpolation.

280 For ease of use, the processes and models are grouped into alternative Geant4–DNA
281 physics constructors. The existence of different physics constructors in Geant4–DNA reflects
282 the continuous efforts to be able to perform track structure simulations for electrons in
283 condensed media with improved accuracy and reduced computational effort. Unfortunately,
284 the absence of experimental data in the liquid-water phase does not allow them to be strictly
285 validated. Three alternative constructors are tested in this work: Geant4–DNA *Option2*,
286 *Option4* and *Option6*. They contain alternative electron models and, for now, use similar
287 proton, helium, and ion models. The emphasis given on electrons stems from the fact that
288 they exist as secondaries from the ionisation of atoms of the medium under study and are
289 responsible for the spatial energy deposition of radiation in matter.

290 Both Geant4–DNA *Option2* and *Option4* physics constructors (called here *Geant4–*
291 *DNA–Opt2* and *Geant4–DNA–Opt4*) are based on the dielectric theory of inelastic scat-
292 tering, where condensed phase effects are included through the use of a material-dependent
293 function for the computation of the corresponding cross sections (ionisation, electronic excita-

tion) for electrons. *Geant4-DNA-Opt4* is an improved version of *Geant4-DNA-Opt2* which, among other improvements, uses a refined partitioning algorithm, leading to higher ion-pair energies, smaller penetration distances, and less diffused dose-point kernels, and performs simulations in a more accurate manner at the lower energy range (Kyriakou et al.³⁸). Its extended relativistic version has recently been developed and will be available in a future version of Geant4-DNA. The Geant4-DNA *Option6* physics constructor, called here *Geant4-DNA-Opt6*, is a re-engineering of the original CPA100 code for electrons (Terrissol and Beaudre³⁹). It adopts the Binary Encounter Bethe formalism (Kim and Rudd⁴⁰, Bordage et al.⁴¹) for the analytical computation of ionisation cross sections and the dielectric response function formalism for the computation of electronic excitation. The three Geant4-DNA physics constructors under study cover a different energy range of applicability for electrons and, for convenience, since Geant4 version 11.1, the default high energy limits of *Geant4-DNA-Opt4* and *Geant4-DNA-Opt6* for electrons have been extended up to 1 MeV using the inelastic cross sections of the *Geant4-DNA-Opt2* constructor. Different approaches are provided for the implementation of elastic scattering, which is of critical importance in the spatial deposition of energy because of the deflections suffered by the electrons, in the three constructors. All models, including the relevant processes for protons, neutral hydrogen atoms, helium nuclei and their charge states, and ions, are further described in the 2018 Geant4-DNA review (Incerti et al.³⁶). Further, the upper energy limit for proton transport was increased from 100 MeV to 300 MeV by incorporating excitation and ionization models based on the Relativistic Plane Wave Born Approximation (RPWBA) (Domínguez-Muñoz et al.⁴²). Geant4 photon processes (photoelectric effect, Compton scattering, gamma conversion, Rayleigh scattering) and models (Livermore, Klein-Nishina, 5D and Livermore, respectively, documented in Section IV.A.) are also available in these constructors.

III.B. Geant4-DNA chemistry constructors

Water molecules that have been ionised and excited through interactions with primary and secondary particles participate in a decomposition process through dissociation channels. These energetically charged water fragments undergo a sequence of breakdown processes, rapidly generating primary water radiolysis products such as H_3O^+ , $\bullet\text{OH}$, $\text{H}\bullet$, OH^- and H_2 (Karamitros et al.⁴³). Sub-excited electrons gradually undergo a thermalisation process to

324 reach thermal equilibrium at about 0.025 eV to form solvated electrons.

325 In Geant4–DNA, it is assumed that primary water radiolysis species and solvated elec-
326 trons form within 1 ps, after which they are expected to diffuse through Brownian dynamics
327 and eventually react. The diffusion and reaction of species through these initial hetero-
328 geneous distributions (spurs) along the tracks are described by either the Step–By–Step
329 (SBS) approach (Karamitros et al.^{43,44}) or the IRT approach with two model variants: IRT
330 (Ramos–Méndez et al.⁴⁵, Karamitros et al.⁴⁶) and IRT–sync (Tran et al.⁴⁷). While SBS
331 transports species in discrete steps (or time steps Δt) through Brownian motion until a
332 chemical encounter defines a reaction, the IRT model tends to directly calculate a reaction
333 probability. The IRT approach assumes that reactions are independent and that the diffu-
334 sion of reactants from their initial positions to the reaction site is not influenced by other
335 chemical species or volume boundaries. In this context, on the basis of reaction probabili-
336 ties, the reaction times can be sampled for every potential pair of reactants. These times are
337 then sorted in ascending order, creating a list of potential reactions. Reactions are processed
338 sequentially, starting with those with the shortest reaction time. Products formed from re-
339 actions in progress may undergo further reactions with other reactants, thereby being added
340 to the reaction list.

341 Since IRT models optimise the diffusion actions, this approach has a much better com-
342 putational performance than the SBS model, especially when dealing with a large number
343 of species. The synchronous IRT (IRT–sync documented in Tran et al.⁴⁷) model proposes
344 an implementation of the IRT model to allow access to spatial–temporal information at cer-
345 tain times. This implementation uses as the time step the randomly sampled time given by
346 the IRT model until the next expected reaction. In other words, instead of optimising the
347 time step to the next reaction like the SBS model does, the IRT–sync model calculates the
348 reaction time directly using the IRT model. This procedure is repeated until the end of the
349 simulation. This means that after each time step, it is necessary to synchronise the time and
350 position of all diffusing species. This is a drawback of the IRT–sync approach. However, due
351 to synchronisation at each time step, IRT–sync provides users with spatio–temporal infor-
352 mation for all chemical species, which can then be coupled with information on geometric
353 boundaries or the biological target.

354 The chemistry constructors in Geant4–DNA specify the dissociation scheme (see Ta-

ble 2), the chemical reactions and the models involved in water radiolysis. In Geant4 11.1, Geant4–DNA provides *G4EmDNAChemistry* (*chem_default*), *G4EmDNAChemistry_option1* (*chem_option1*), *G4EmDNAChemistry_option2* (*chem_option2*), and *G4EmDNAChemistry_option3* (*chem_option3*) that deploy different sets of reactions concerning water radiolysis and DNA reactions, accompanied by reaction constant data. While *chem_default*, *chem_option1*, and *chem_option2* constructors use a dissociation scheme following the PARTRAC code (Friedland et al.⁴⁸), the chemistry constructor *chem_option3* applies the B1A1 dissociation channel proposed by the TRACs code (Shin et al.⁴⁹, Cobut et al.⁵⁰). *chem_default*, *chem_option1*, and *chem_option2* use the SBS model by default, while in the chemistry constructor *chem_option3*, an user interface allows users to choose either SBS, IRT or IRT–sync.

Process		Channel	<i>chem_option3</i> Shin et al. ⁵¹	<i>chem_default</i> <i>chem_option1</i> <i>chem_option2</i> Karamitros et al. ⁴³
			Branching ratios	
Ionisation	H_2O^+	$\text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \bullet\text{OH}$	100	100
Excitation	A^1B_1	$\text{H}^\bullet + \bullet\text{OH}$	65	65
		$\text{H}_2\text{O} + \Delta\text{E}$	35	35
		B^1A_1	$\text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \bullet\text{OH} + \text{e}_{aq}^-$	50
	$\text{H}^\bullet + \bullet\text{OH}$		25.35	-
	$\text{H}_2 + 2 \bullet\text{OH}$		3.25	15
	$2\text{H}^\bullet + \text{O}(^3\text{P})^*$		3.9	-
	Rydberg A+B, C+D, Diffuse bands	$\text{H}_2\text{O} + \Delta\text{E}$	17.5	30
		$\text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \bullet\text{OH} + \text{e}_{aq}^-$	50	50
			$\text{H}_2\text{O} + \Delta\text{E}$	50
	Electron capture	DEA	$\text{OH}^- + \bullet\text{OH} + \text{H}_2$	100
Recombination		$\text{H}^\bullet + \bullet\text{OH}$	35.75	55
		$\text{H}_2 + 2 \bullet\text{OH}$	13.65	15
		$2\text{H}^\bullet + \text{O}(^3\text{P})^*$	15.6	-
		$\text{H}_2\text{O} + \Delta\text{E}$	35	30

Table 2: Dissociation schemes and branching ratios available in the four chemistry constructors (*chem_default*, *chem_option1*, *chem_option2* and *chem_option3*). *: Oxygen atom in triplet state P. Geant4 version 11.1 is considered.

366 III.C. Low energy electron Dose Point Kernels test

367 This test is described in detail in Arce et al.¹ and is of interest for the application of the
368 Geant4–DNA extensions in dosimetry calculations in radiopharmaceutical therapy (Prest-
369 wick et al.⁵², Simpkin and Mackie⁵³).

370 Mono–energetic electrons, with energy 10, 15 and 100 keV, are emitted isotropically
371 into a 4π solid angle from a point source placed in a spherical liquid water (defined as
372 G4_WATER) volume. Radial energy deposition profiles are calculated.

373 The test, originally included in the G4–Med suite to benchmark Geant4 electromagnetic
374 physics constructors using a Condensed History approach (Arce et al.¹), has been adapted
375 to benchmark Geant4–DNA physics lists, as track structure codes are recognised to be more
376 accurate to calculate energy deposition distributions in volumes with sub–cellular dimensions
377 (Braby et al.⁵⁴). Geant4–DNA physics constructors *Geant4–DNA–Opt2*, *Geant4–DNA–Opt4*
378 and *Geant4–DNA–Opt6* are tested. This is a pure regression test between different versions
379 of Geant4.

380 Figure 2 shows the results of the test. We observe that *Geant4–DNA–Opt2* and *Geant4–*
381 *DNA–Opt4* provide similar results, while *Geant4–DNA–Opt6* estimates the peak of the en-
382 ergy deposition distribution slightly closer to the source of the incident electrons.

383 III.D. The Microdosimetry test

384 The *Microdosimetry* test is based on the Geant4 advanced example *microyz*. The test was
385 already existing in the G4–Med benchmarking system (Arce et al.¹) but it has been re-
386 vised and adapted to test *Geant4–DNA–Opt2*, *Geant4–DNA–Opt4* and *Geant4–DNA–Opt6*.
387 It calculates microdosimetric spectra of lineal and specific energy and their corresponding
388 frequency-weighted and dose-weighted quantities for the case of monoenergetic electrons
389 traversing liquid water spheres, randomly placed along the track structure of the incident
390 electron in a semi-infinite water medium (Kyriakou et al.¹⁷).

Figure 2: Top plots: Dose Point Kernel in water, obtained for 10, 15 and 100 keV electrons. Bottom plots: Ratio of the results obtained with either Geant4-DNA physics list *Geant4-DNA-Opt4* or *Geant4-DNA-Opt6* and *Geant4-DNA-Opt2*. Results obtained with the *LowEElectDPK* test and Geant4 11.1.

391 III.D.1. Simulation set-up

392 Monoenergetic electrons are incident on liquid water with monochromatic energies equal to
 393 100 eV, 1 keV, 10 keV, 100 keV and 1 MeV, covering both the imaging and therapeutic
 394 range, i.e. primary and secondary electrons relevant to radiation therapy applications, like
 395 hadrontherapy and radionuclide therapy (Kyriakou et al. ⁵⁵). The sensitive volume sphere
 396 has a diameter of 10 nm, which is a mean distance of interest for studies like Double Strand
 397 Break induction (Verhaegen and Reniers ⁵⁶). Additionally, spheres with a 100 nm diameter
 398 are also investigated here as they are used in biophysical models for radiation action ⁵⁷.
 399 Finally, spheres with a 1 μm diameter are considered as they are of interest for Tissue
 400 Equivalent Proportional Counter measurements for radiation protection (Nikjoo et al. ⁵⁸).

401 The test is used for regression testing purposes only, to study how changes in the
 402 physics models of Geant4 impact the calculation of microdosimetric quantities. In this study,
 403 we present results for the dose-mean lineal energy, which is the dose-weighted probability
 404 function of the lineal energy that takes into account the higher dose deposition of the greater
 405 valued lineal energies Rosenfeld et al. ⁵⁹. In the *microyz* example, the dose-mean lineal energy

406 is calculated by summing over all the lineal energies y_i ¹ calculated in each track i , times the
 407 contribution of each y_i to the dose within the sensitive volume under study.

$$408 \quad \langle y_D \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^N d_i y_i \quad (5)$$

409 with $d_i = f_i y_i / \langle y_F \rangle$, $\langle y_F \rangle$ being the frequency-weighted lineal energy calculated
 410 by $\langle y_F \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^N f_i y_i$, f_i the probability weighting factor and N the total number of tracks
 411 (histories) simulated including primary and secondary particles. The lineal energies y_i for
 412 each track i , are calculated in the Geant4 code by randomly placing a sphere of a user defined
 413 size along a certain distance from an energy deposit within the track. Details on the algorithm
 414 followed in the *microyz* example can be found in Kyriakou et al.^{17, 55}. The energy cut-off is
 415 kept equal to 10 eV for the three physics constructors investigated and the sub-excitation
 416 processes are deactivated. The statistics for each energy varies according to the incident
 417 energy in order to avoid very large simulation times and achieve a statistical fluctuation
 418 below 1% . In the *geant-val* testing suite, the three Geant4-DNA physics constructors
 419 mentioned above are compared up to 10 keV because this is the upper limit of applicability
 420 of the specific electron elastic and inelastic models used in *Geant4-DNA-Opt4* (Kyriakou
 421 et al.³⁸).

422 III.D.2. Results

423 Figure 3 shows the dose-mean lineal energy, y_D , as a function of the incident electron ki-
 424 netic energy. Results are reported for Geant4 11.1. For a water sphere of 10 nm diameter,
 425 differences between the three physics constructors are more pronounced compared to the
 426 larger diameters. *Geant4-DNA-Opt6* produced y_D values higher than those calculated with
 427 *Geant4-DNA-Opt2*, with a maximum difference of 25%. These differences are caused by
 428 the much different inelastic cross sections of this constructor. Overall, differences between
 429 *Geant4-DNA-Opt2* and *Geant4-DNA-Opt4* are smaller as a result of the similar inelastic
 430 models with the differences attributed to the particular ionization and excitation contri-
 431 butions in each model. Additionally, *Geant4-DNA-Opt6* contains energy loss for elastic
 432 scattering that leads to a decrease of the frequency mean lineal energy values³⁸ and espe-

¹The lineal energy is calculated as the ratio of the energy imparted to the matter in a given volume by a single energy-deposition event and the mean chord length of that volume⁵⁴.

433 cially in the case of smaller diameters (not shown in this study) but does not affect the
434 y_D . In the case of 100 nm and 1 μm diameter water sphere, the different Geant4-DNA
435 physics constructors produce smaller differences; up to 6% for *Geant4-DNA-Opt6* and up
436 to 3% for *Geant4-DNA-Opt2*. It must be taken into consideration that above 10 keV for
437 *Geant4-DNA-Opt4* and 256 keV for *Geant4-DNA-Opt6*, the *Geant4-DNA-Opt2* physics
438 constructor is used and we expect that the comparison would be more rigorous if each model
439 was used up to 1 MeV, which will be shown in a future work. In any case, the low (espe-
440 cially the sub-keV) energy behaviour affects the energy deposition distribution at sub-micron
441 volumes.

Figure 3: Left plots: Dose—mean lineal energy y_D with respect to the kinetic energy of the incident electrons, for a water sphere of 10 nm (top), 100 nm (middle) and 1 μm diameter (bottom). Right plot: Ratio of the results obtained with either *Geant4-DNA-Opt4* or *Geant4-DNA-Opt6* with the default *Geant4-DNA-Opt2*. Results obtained with the *microz* test and Geant4 11.1.

442 III.E. The chemistry test

443 The *Chemistry* test is based on the Geant4 extended example *chem6*, which illustrates how
444 to compute radiochemical yields (G-values) versus time or Linear Energy Transfer (LET).
445 The time-dependent radiolytic yield is often defined as the number of molecules, at a given
446 time, for 100 eV of deposited energy. To reduce simulation execution times, in Geant4-DNA,
447 the G-values are calculated for a short energy range of the ionizing particle that is referred
448 to as the "track segment G-value". Two parameters are used for energy threshold selection,
449 the minimum energy deposition *eLossMin* and the maximum energy deposition *eLossMax*.
450 While the simulation is aborted if the total energy deposition of a simulated event (that is,
451 the primary particle and all associated secondaries) is larger than *eLossMax*, the incident
452 particle is killed if its energy loss exceeds *eLossMin*⁵¹.

453 The *chem6* Geant4 example uses the chemistry constructor *chem_option3*. This con-
454 structor offers users an interface to facilitate the addition or removal of chemical reactions
455 or evaluate the influence of chemical reaction-diffusion models, such as the Step-By-Step
456 (*SBS*), the Independent Time Reaction (*IRT*) and the synchronized Independent Time Re-
457 action (*IRT-sync*) models, on water radiolysis simulations.

458 III.E.1. Simulation set-up

459 In this test, we perform a simulation to compute time-dependent G-values for the chemical
460 models *SBS*, *IRT* and *IRT-sync*, for 1 MeV incident electrons with *eLossMin* and *eLossMax*
461 equal to 10 keV and 10.1 keV, respectively. Table 3 shows the reaction list and reaction
462 constants used in the test.

463

464 III.E.2. Results and Discussion

465 Figure 4 shows the G-values of e_{aq}^- , H_2O_2 and $\bullet OH$ species, calculated using the *SBS*, *IRT-*
466 *sync* and *IRT* models, against available experimental measurements (Shiraishi et al.⁶⁰, LaV-
467 erne⁶¹, Wang et al.⁶²). The G-values are calculated with Geant4 11.1. Figure 5 shows the
468 ratio of the G-values calculated with either *IRT* or *IRT-sync* and *SBS*.

469 In the case of e_{aq}^- , *IRT* produces similar results to *SBS* within approximately 0.1 ns

Reaction	k_{obs} $\times 10^{10} M^{-1} s^{-1}$	Partially diffusion- controlled	Totally diffusion- controlled
$H^\bullet + e_{aq}^- + H_2O \rightarrow OH^- + H_2$	2.5		X
$H^\bullet + \bullet OH \rightarrow H_2O$	1.55	X	
$H^\bullet + H^\bullet \rightarrow H_2$	0.503		X
$H_2O_2 + e_{aq}^- \rightarrow OH^- + \bullet OH$	1.1	X	
$H_3O^+ + e_{aq}^- \rightarrow H^\bullet + H_2O$	2.11	X	
$H_3O^+ + OH^- \rightarrow 2H_2O$	11.3		X
$\bullet OH + e_{aq}^- \rightarrow OH^-$	2.95	X	
$\bullet OH + \bullet OH \rightarrow H_2O_2$	0.55	X	
$e_{aq}^- + e_{aq}^- + 2H_2O \rightarrow 2OH^- + H_2$	0.636		X

Table 3: Reactions and associated reaction rate coefficients used by *IRT* and *IRT-sync* are either partially or totally diffusion-controlled. *SBS* considers that all reactions are totally diffusion-controlled reactions.

470 from the start of the chemical stage. After that, it produces lower G-values with a maximum
471 difference of about 5% at 1 μs . *IRT-sync* underestimates the e_{aq}^- G-values of about 1%–5%
472 with respect to the *SBS*. In the case of H_2O_2 , both *IRT* and *IRT-sync* produce higher
473 G-values (about 1.3 and 2 times higher, respectively) at the start of the chemical stage
474 when compared to *SBS*. After that, the difference decreases with time. In the case of $\bullet OH$
475 G-values, both *IRT* and *IRT-sync* produce consistently lower G-values (differences up to
476 4% and 6%, respectively, when compared to *SBS*).

477 Figure 6 reports the ratio of the results obtained with Geant4 11.1 and the reference
478 experimental data (Shiraishi et al. ⁶⁰, LaVerne ⁶¹, Wang et al. ⁶²). The three chemistry models
479 of Geant4 agree with the reference data within the uncertainty affecting the experimental
480 measurements.

Figure 4: G-values of e_{aq}^- , H_2O_2 and $\bullet OH$ species calculated with the *chemistry* test, using the *SBS*, *IRT-sync* and *IRT* models. Results obtained with Geant4 11.1.

Figure 5: Ratio of G-values (plotted in Figure 4) obtained with *IRT-sync* and *IRT* models, when compared to SBS.

Figure 6: Ratio of G-values obtained with *SBS*, *IRT* and *IRT-sync* (Geant4 11.1) and experimental data (Shiraishi et al. ⁶⁰, LaVerne ⁶¹, Wang et al. ⁶²)

481 IV. Electromagnetic physics benchmarking tests

482 The electromagnetic (EM) physics tests listed in Table 1 have been executed with
 483 Geant4 11.1 via the *geant-val* system. Following the methodology described in
 484 Arce et al.¹, the EM physics constructors under study are *G4EmLivermorePhysics*,
 485 *G4EmPenelopePhysics*, *G4EmStandardPhysics_option3* and *G4EmStandardPhysics_option4*,
 486 called here *Livermore*, *Penelope*, *Opt3* and *Opt4*, respectively. The EM physics constructor
 487 *G4EmStandardPhysicsSS*, called here *SS*, is considered in the backscattering test (see Sec-
 488 tion IV.E.1.) as it uses the single scattering model to describe the Coulomb scattering. The
 489 EM constructor *G4EmStandardPhysics* has been excluded from the benchmarking study as
 490 our previous work (Arce et al.¹) demonstrated that it is not appropriate for bio-medical
 491 applications.

492 The EM physics constructors under study have been documented in Arce et al.¹ and
 493 their evolution between Geant4 10.5 and 11.1 is reported in Section IV.A.. Sections IV.B.,
 494 IV.C. and IV.D. describe the new tests, *brachytherapy* with an ¹²⁵I source, *MV X-ray ra-*
 495 *diotherapy* and *Electron FLASH radiotherapy*, respectively. Section IV.E. reports significant
 496 findings resulting from the regression testing of all the other tests, described in Arce et al.¹,
 497 between Geant4 10.5 and 11.1.

498 IV.A. Evolution of the Geant4 electromagnetic physics construc- 499 tors under study

500 *Livermore*, *Penelope*, *Opt3* and *Opt4* EM constructors correspond to different combinations
 501 of models deriving from either Geant4 *Standard*, *Livermore* or *Penelope* packages (Geant4
 502 Physics Reference Manual⁶³, Arce et al.¹). For a detailed description of the EM constructors,
 503 the reader can refer to Arce et al.¹, while here only significant revisions between Geant4 10.5
 504 and 11.1 are commented.

505 Table 4 lists the Geant4 11.1 configuration of processes and corresponding models in
 506 each EM constructor studied in this work. Since Geant4 11.1, the *Livermore* physics pro-
 507 cesses use by default the newly introduced EPICS2017 (Electron-Photon Interaction Cross
 508 Sections) (Cullen^{64,65}, Li et al.⁶⁶) data libraries to describe Rayleigh scattering, photoelec-
 509 tric effect, Compton scattering, and gamma conversion processes. Also these models of

510 Rayleigh scattering and photoelectric effect are used in the *Opt3* and *Opt4* constructors.
511 The *G4BetheHeitler5DModel* (Bernard^{67, 68}), is used for sampling of final state of gamma
512 conversion to electron-positron pair in *Opt3*, *Opt4*, and *Livermore* EM configurations. In
513 Geant4 11.1, in *Opt4*, the Penelope model substitutes the Livermore model to describe the
514 ionisation process of electrons with energy below 100 keV.

515 All the EM constructors use the same EM physics models for protons. The only change
516 between Geant4 10.5 and 11.1 is the adoption of ICRU90 stopping power data for water,
517 air, and graphite. For the other materials, NIST PSTAR data are used if available. If not,
518 stopping powers are computed using ICRU49 evaluated data. A novel feature in Geant4 11.1
519 is that all the EM constructors, used in this report, include a new ionization model for ions
520 heavier than Helium, the *G4LindhardSorensenIonModel*⁶³. In this model, the ICRU90 and
521 ICRU73 data for stopping power are used below $2MeV/u$.

522 Table 5 reports multiple scattering parameters and other options. Differences between
523 Geant4 10.5 and 11.1 are highlighted in bold. A significant change between Geant4 10.5
524 and 11.1 is that in *Opt3* the *RangeFactor* has been changed from 0.04 to 0.03 and that the
525 use of step limitation algorithm for multiple scattering (Ivanchenko et al.⁶⁹) *UseDistance-*
526 *ToBoundary* has been substituted with *UseSafetyPlus*, with the intent of providing faster
527 simulation, more robust tracking in magnetic field and more accurate simulation results for
528 electron and positron back-scattering. In the *SS* EM constructors, the use of the step limi-
529 tation algorithm for multiple scattering *UseDistanceToBoundary* has been substituted with
530 *UseSafetyPlus*.

Geant4	WVI	Opt3	SS	Opt4	Livermore	Penelope
Rayleigh scattering and photoelectric effect			Livermore (EPICS2017) Li et al. ⁶⁶			PENELOPE
Compton scattering	<i>G4KleinNishina Model</i>			<i>G4LowEPComptonModel</i> for E < 20 MeV Brown et al. ⁷⁰ , <i>G4KleinNishina</i> for E > 20 MeV	Livermore (EPICS2017) Li et al. ⁶⁶	PENELOPE
Gamma conversion			<i>G4BethetheHestler5DModel</i> Bernard ^{67, 68}		<i>G4Livermore5DModel</i> Li et al. ⁶⁶	PENELOPE
e ⁻ and e ⁺ ionisation	Standard			PENELOPE for E < 100 keV , Standard for E > 100 keV	Livermore for E < 100 keV Standard for E > 100 keV	PENELOPE
e ⁻ and e ⁺ bremsstrahlung	Geant4 <i>Standard Model</i>			<i>G4SeltzerBergerModel</i> for E < 1 GeV, <i>G4eBremsstrahlungRelModel</i> for E > 1 GeV		PENELOPE
e ⁺ annihilation	<i>G4eplusTo2GammaOKVMModel</i> ⁶³			Standard		PENELOPE
e ⁻ and e ⁺ multiple scattering	Urban model for E < 1 MeV, Wentzel model for E > 1 MeV	Urban model	Not available		Goudsmit-Saunderson model (Incerti et al. ⁷¹) for E < 100 MeV Wentzel model for E > 100 MeV	
Coulomb scattering	on	off			on	
Bremsstrahlung angular distribution	<i>Modified Tsai</i>	<i>2BS</i>	<i>Modified Tsai</i>		<i>2BS</i>	PENELOPE

Table 4: Geant4 physics models to describe EM physics processes up to 1 GeV, in the Geant4 EM constructors under investigation. Geant4 11.1 is considered. For details on the models the reader should refer to the Geant4 Physics Reference Manual ⁶³. Changes with respect to Geant4 10.5 are shown in bold.

Geant4 EM parameter	<i>Opt3</i>	<i>Opt4</i> <i>Livermore</i> <i>Penelope</i>	<i>SS</i>
<i>Minimum energy (eV)</i>	10.	100.	100.
<i>Lowest electron energy (keV)</i>	0.1	0.1	0.01
<i>Number of bins per decade</i>	20	20	7
<i>Mott corrections</i>	on	on	on
<i>dRoverRange</i> for e^- and e^+	0.2	0.2	0.2
<i>finalRange</i> for e^- and e^+ (mm)	0.1	0.01	1.
<i>dRoverRange</i> for muons and hadrons	0.2	0.1	0.2
<i>finalRange</i> (mm) for muons and hadrons	0.05	0.05	0.1
<i>Skin for e^- and e^+</i>	1	3	1
<i>Range factor</i> for e^- and e^+	0.03	0.08	0.04
<i>Range factor</i> for muons and hadrons	0.2	0.2	0.2
Msc StepLimitType	<i>fUseSafetyPlus</i>*		
Fluorescence and Auger e^-	on		
PIXE modelling	off	off	on

Table 5: Geant4 EM parameters of the EM constructors under investigation. Geant4 11.1 is considered. *: the use of *fUseSafetyPlus* is a new feature for the EM constructor *Opt3* and *SS*. Changes with respect to Geant4 10.5 are shown in bold.

531 IV.B. Brachytherapy test – ^{125}I source

532 Since the publication of Arce et al.¹, the *Brachytherapy* test, which is released with Geant4
533 as an advanced example, has been extended to calculate the radial dose rate distribution of
534 an OncuraTM brachytherapy ^{125}I Model 6711 source in water. The test has been included
535 in the *geant-val* interface as an option of the *Brachytherapy* test. The results of the simula-
536 tion are compared with reference data published in Dolan et al.⁷², which are experimental
537 measurements performed with TLD detectors.

538 IV.B.1. Simulation set-up

539 The Oncura Model 6711, described in Dolan et al.⁷² has been implemented in the Geant4
540 simulation. The ^{125}I source emission is obtained by modelling the radioactive decay of iodine
541 with the Geant4 *General Particle Source*. The iodine radioactive core is a cylinder with 0.247
542 mm radius and the length of the cylinder is 2.794 mm. These lengths take into account that
543 the radioactive coating is implanted 3 μm deep onto the surface of the silver core. The ^{125}I
544 source is modeled in the center of a water box (modeled as G4_WATER) with 30 cm size.
545 The energy deposition is scored with a Geant4 scoring mesh with voxels 0.25 mm wide and
546 the threshold of production of secondary particles is set equal to 0.05 mm. The radial dose
547 rate distribution is calculated as the energy deposition per unit of mass, along the transverse
548 axis of the source, 90° from the source axis. 10^{10} histories are executed to obtain a statistical
549 uncertainty which is lower than 1% for distances up to 10 cm from the brachytherapeutic source.

550 The reference data are experimental measurements performed with thermoluminescent
551 dosimeters, which are documented in Dolan et al.⁷².

552 IV.B.2. Results and discussion

553 Figure 7 shows the radial dose rate distribution in water produced by the ^{125}I brachytherapy
554 source, calculated with Geant4 11.1 and compared to the reference data. The agreement
555 between the two data sets is within the experimental uncertainty affecting the experimental
556 values, for all the Geant4 EM constructors tested.

Figure 7: Left: Radial dose rate distribution with respect to the distance from the source, calculated with the *Brachy* test in the case of an ^{125}I Oncura 6711 source. Right: Ratio of the simulation and experimental data (Dolan et al. ⁷²). Geant4 11.1 is used. To note, the two plots have different scales on the x-axis.

557 IV.C. MV X-ray radiotherapy test

558 The *MV X-ray radiotherapy* test is released in Geant4 as the advanced example *Medi-*
 559 *cal_Linac*. Since its first version (Caccia et al. ⁷³), the code has undergone significant en-
 560 hancements, including the integration of multithreading capabilities and the incorporation
 561 of experimental dosimetric data, along with a comprehensive geometric description based on
 562 a real linear accelerator. The experimental dosimetric data and the description of the linear
 563 accelerator are derived from the intercomparison of Monte Carlo simulations for a medi-
 564 cal linear accelerator conducted by Working Group Computational Dosimetry of Eurados
 565 (Caccia et al. ^{74, 75}). The code replicates a GE Saturne 43 linear accelerator. The detailed
 566 description of the accelerator and the phantom are provided in the EURADOS Report (Cac-
 567 cia et al. ⁷⁵). This report also contains the dosimetric data acquired with the GE Saturne 43
 568 accelerator at Laboratoire National Henri Becquerel (CEA, LIST, LNE LNHB). The energy
 569 and dimension of the electron source, and the field size can be easily adjusted via a macro
 570 file. In the example a liquid water phantom is implemented for the computation of the dose
 571 distribution in 3D.

Figure 8: Schematic view of the simulation set-up for the Medical Linac advanced example, based on the geometry of the Saturne 43 General Electric linear accelerator. The 10x10 cm² field size is defined at 100 cm from the source, 10 cm below the phantom surface. The diagram is not to scale.

Beamline component	thickness (mm)	cut (mm)
Target	4	1.0
Primary Collimator	79 + 57.5	10.0
Flattening Filter	min 7.5, max 46.8	1.5
Secondary Collimator	40.5	10.0
Phantom	5 (voxel side)	0.1

Table 6: Production cuts used in the components of the beamline.

602 IV.C.2. Results and discussion

603 The reported data were obtained using Geant4.11.1. 2×10^{11} primary events are set to enable
 604 the simulation of the dose distribution in a water phantom positioned at a distance of 90
 605 cm from the linear accelerator source with an uncertainty of lower than 1% and 2% in the
 606 longitudinal and transverse profile, respectively.

607 In Figure 9 are reported the normalised dose profile along the longitudinal axis, and
 608 the transverse dose profile at a depth of 10 cm in the water phantom for all tested EM
 609 constructors (*Opt3*, *Opt4*, *Livermore*, and *Penelope*). The normalisation is performed, for
 610 each of them, to the dose value at a depth of 10 cm for the longitudinal profile, and on
 611 the longitudinal axis for the transverse profile. The results concerning the longitudinal dose
 612 distribution show an agreement between the simulation results obtained with *Opt3*, *Opt4*,
 613 *Livermore* and *Penelope* and the experimental data within 2.5%. Differences in the build-up

Figure 9: Results of the Medical Linac test obtained with Geant4.11.1. Top left: Longitudinal dose distribution in the water phantom. The curves are normalised to the dose value at a depth of 10 cm. Top right: Transverse dose distribution at 10 cm depth in the water phantom. The curves are normalised on the longitudinal axis. Bottom: ratios of between simulated experimental data for the longitudinal (left) and transverse (right) profile. Experimental data from Caccia et al. ⁷⁵.

614 region go up to about 5%, posing challenges for precise ion chamber measurements in this
 615 area. The relative statistical uncertainties associated to the simulated data (longitudinal
 616 dose distribution) is 0.5% for the EM constructors *Opt3*, *Opt4*, *Livermore*, and 0.4% for
 617 *Penelope*.

618 For the transverse dose distribution (10 cm below the water phantom surface), simulated
 619 and experimental data are in agreement within 3% in the field for the EM constructors *Opt3*,
 620 *Opt4*, and *Livermore*. Discrepancies at the edge of the field area are attributed to the high
 621 dose gradient of this region where the uncertainty in the position is critical. The difference

622 between simulated and experimental data in the out of field area is under investigation.

Figure 10: Transverse dose profiles simulated with the full EM constructors *Opt4*, *Penelope*, and *Opt4* using the bremsstrahlung model *G4PenelopeBremsstrahlungModel*.

623 The relative statistical uncertainties associated to the simulated data (transverse dose
 624 distribution) is 1.9% for the EM constructors *Opt3*, *Opt4*, *Penelope*, and 2% for *Liver-*
 625 *more*. In particular, the transverse profile obtained with *Penelope* shows a poor match
 626 even in the field area, probably because the Penelope bremsstrahlung model used in our
 627 version of Geant4 is not suitable for this type of application (Arce et al.³¹). In order
 628 to isolate the source of the problem we performed a simulation using the *Opt4* construc-
 629 tor and substituting its bremsstrahlung model (*G4eBremsstrahlung*) with the *Penelope*
 630 *G4PenelopeBremsstrahlungModel* model, the results are reported in Figure 10.

631 IV.D. Electron FLASH radiotherapy test

632 Among the most innovative radiotherapeutic techniques recently developed, FLASH radiother-
 633 apy, consisting of using ultra-high dose rate (UHDR) particle beams (40 Gy/s), is attracting
 634 an increasing interest in the medical physics community.

635 Pre-clinical studies have shown that the use of UHDR beams may substantially im-
 636 prove normal tissue sparing (so-called FLASH effect) while maintaining the same tumour
 637 control probability (TCP) compared to conventional dose-rate radiotherapy (Favaudon
 638 et al.⁸⁰, Vozenin M-C⁸¹). A clinical translation of FLASH radiotherapy certainly requires

639 the establishment of new protocols and guidelines for the beam delivery, and absolute and
640 reference dosimetry (Romano et al.⁸²).

641 For this reason, an extensive effort is currently dedicated to accurately model with Monte
642 Carlo simulations the accelerator machines and the generated radiation field, to be able to
643 predict the beam quality and parameters at the irradiation point. In this context, within
644 the framework of a consolidated collaboration between the CPFR (Centro Pisano Flash Ra-
645 diotherapy) in Pisa and the INFN Catania Division, Italy, a Triode Electron Gun Equipped
646 ElectronFlash Linac, manufactured by Sordina Iort Technologies S.p.A., was simulated in
647 Geant4. The Linac, installed at the CPFR (DiMartino et al.^{83, 84}) is able to accelerate 7 and
648 9 MeV pulsed electron beams at UHDR regime, and the device has been recently simulated
649 in Geant4 and released in the advanced example *eFLASH_radiotherapy*.

650 The test, presented here, is based on the *eFLASH_radiotherapy* Geant4 advanced ex-
651 ample. It calculates and benchmarks the lateral dose distribution obtained at the reference
652 position, namely 13 mm water depth, and the depth-dose distribution in water obtained at
653 the exit of the applicator, with experimental data acquired during the commissioning phase
654 of the EF linac in Pisa and reported in DiMartino et al.⁸⁴.

655 IV.D.1. Simulation set-up

656 The simulation set-up models accurately the geometrical configuration experimentally used
657 in the pre-clinical research performed at the CPFR.

658 The primary radiation field is modeled as a $2.5 \times 2.5 \text{ mm}^2$ electron source with an energy
659 spectrum peaked at 9 MeV which realistically reproduces the energy spectrum of electrons
660 accelerated by the EF LINAC. The realistic energy spectrum was provided for the G4MED
661 test by the manufacturer (SIT Sordina) to assure a direct comparison of the simulations
662 with the experimental data. For copyright reasons, a slightly modified version of the LINAC
663 geometry and source energy spectrum is included in the published *eFLASH_radiotherapy*
664 advanced example.

665 A water phantom is added downstream the accelerator at a distance of 73 cm. A
666 plexiglass 73 cm long cylindrical hollow applicator with 10 cm internal diameter is added to
667 shape the field size and obtain a uniform dose distribution with a flat lateral profile⁸⁴.

Figure 11: Schematic view of the simulation set-up of the electron FLASH radiotherapy test.

668 The depth–dose distribution along the water phantom is calculated using a scoring mesh
 669 with size $60 \times 2 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$. The mesh is divided in 60 voxels along the x axis (the voxel size is
 670 then $1 \times 2 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$). The vertical transversal profile is retrieved at 13 mm depth in the water
 671 phantom, which corresponds to the maximum expected dose in the depth–dose distribution
 672 (DiMartino et al. ⁸⁴). To calculate the transversal dose profile, a second scoring mesh has
 673 been added with size $1 \times 120 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$. This has been divided in 60 voxels along the y axis
 674 (the voxel size is then $1 \times 2 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$). The EM constructors *Opt3*, *Opt4*, *Livermore*, and
 675 *Penelope* are tested. A global production cut of 0.1 mm is used. 10^8 histories are set to
 676 obtain a statistical uncertainty lower than 1%.

677 IV.D.2. Results and discussion

678 Figure 12 shows the longitudinal and the transverse dose distributions in the water phantom
 679 obtained with the electron FLASH radiotherapy test. The results concerning the longitu-
 680 dinal dose distribution show an agreement between the simulation results obtained with
 681 *Opt4*, *Livermore* and *Penelope* within the statistical uncertainty affecting the experimental
 682 data, from the surface of the phantom down to approximately 3.5 cm depth. After that the
 683 agreement deteriorates; to note, at these distances the dose is close to zero. *Opt3* shows
 684 significant differences, up to 20%, from the surface of the water phantom to 1 cm depth.
 685 Then, the agreement is similar to the other physics constructors when compared to the ex-
 686 perimental data. In terms of lateral dose distributions, it can be noted that *Opt4*, *Livermore*
 687 and *Penelope* provide a similar agreement with respect to the reference data, in-field. Out of
 688 field, there are larger differences, up to 50%, which are attributed to the high dose gradient
 689 of this region where the uncertainty in the position can be relevant. *Opt3* underestimates
 690 the dose in-field when compared to the other physics constructors.

691 The large differences found in the depth dose and transverse dose profiles when using
 692 *Opt3* are due to parameters of the multiple scattering model. The *RangeFactor* in Geant4
 693 11.1 is 0.03 and the step limitation option is *UseSafetyPlus* (see Section IV.A.). Based on
 694 results of this test, a Geant4 patch, 11.2.1, has been recently released where both param-
 695 eters were reverted to the Geant4 10.5 variant. Figure 13 shows the new dose distributions
 696 obtained with reverting the multiple scattering parameters of *Opt3* in Geant4 11.2.1. It is
 697 possible to observe that there is a better agreement between Geant4 11.2.1 and the reference
 698 data when compared to Geant4 11.1. Still, there are some discrepancies in the longitudinal
 699 dose distribution, which are under investigation.

Figure 12: Results of the electron FLASH radiotherapy test. Left: Longitudinal dose distribution in the water phantom. The curves are normalised to the maximum dose calculated with *Opt4* (at 17 mm depth in the water phantom). Right: Transverse dose distribution at 13.5 mm depth in the water phantom. The curves are normalised to the maximum dose value obtained with *Opt4*. The plots in the bottom row show the ratio of the Geant4 simulations and reference data reported in DiMartino et al.⁸⁴. Results obtained with Geant4.11.1.

Figure 13: Results of the electron FLASH radiotherapy test, obtained with *Opt3* when the RangeFactor is 0.04 and the step limitation option is *UseDistanceToBoundary*. Results obtained with Geant4 11.2.1. Reference data from DiMartino et al. ⁸⁴.

700 IV.E. Regression testing results

701 The regression testing performed with the electron electronic stopping power test (*ElectD-*
 702 *EDX*), photon attenuation test (*PhotonAttenuation*), monoenergetic x-ray internal breast
 703 dosimetry (*Mammo*) and brachytherapy (*Brachy*) with an ^{192}Ir source have reported no dif-
 704 ferences between Geant4 10.5 and 11.1, and are not documented in this paper. The reader
 705 can refer to the geant-val website¹⁵ and to Archer³² to access the data analysis.

706 IV.E.1. Electron backscattering test

707 This test, documented in Dondero et al.¹⁹ and Arce et al.¹, calculates the fraction of electrons
 708 backscattered by a circular metallic target in vacuum and the backscattering coefficient, η ,
 709 is defined as follows:

$$710 \quad \eta = \frac{e_{\text{back}}}{e_{\text{tot}}} \quad (6)$$

711 where e_{back} is the number of backscattered electrons and e_{tot} is the total number of incident
 712 electrons. The backscattering coefficient has been calculated with the Geant4 EM constructors
 713 *Opt3*, *Opt4*, *SS*, *Livermore* and *Penelope*.

714 In this work, we report the results of the regression testing between Geant4 10.5 and
 715 11.1, considering Be, C, Al, Ti, Mo, Ta and U targets. The energy of the incident electrons
 716 varies from approximately 0.1 keV to 1 MeV. The angle of incidence of the electron beam
 717 varies from 0° to 75° . The simulation results are compared to Sandia Lab experimental data
 718 (Lockwood et al.^{85, 86}). In addition, we report for the first time the benchmarking of the
 719 results of this test against a new experimental data set, obtained within the *EXACRAD*
 720 Project of the European Space Agency².

721 Figure 14 shows exemplary results of the regression testing when the Geant4 calculated
 722 backscattering coefficient is compared against the Sandia Lab experimental data (Lockwood
 723 et al.^{85, 86}). Figure 15 reports the MRE for all the targets under study. It can be noted that
 724 for targets with lower atomic number (Be, C, Al and Ti), *Opt3* and *SS* in Geant4 11.1 tend to

²Results were obtained under ESA Contract 4000121062/17/NL/LF "Experimental Evaluation of ATHENA Charged Particle Background from Secondary Radiation and Scattering in Optics (EXACRAD)". Relevant contribution has been given by Bernard Dirassen, ONERA, and Thierry Paulmier, ONERA, for experimental measurements of electron emission yield and spectra; Paolo Dondero, SWHARD SRL, Fan Lei, RadMod Research Ltd., Alfonso Mantero, SWHARD SRL, for simulations and data analysis; Simone Lotti, INAF IAPS-Roma, Silvano Molendi, INAF IASF-Milano, for coordination and project management.

725 provide less agreement overall to the reference data when compared to Geant4 10.5. Instead,
726 for higher atomic numbers (Ti, Mo, Ta and U), Geant4 11.1 provides a clear improvement
727 for *Opt3* and *SS*. The observed differences in terms of backscattering coefficients are due to
728 modifications of the multiple scattering. Provided that the phenomenon of backscattering
729 is more prominent for targets with higher atomic number, the results of this test show an
730 overall improvement of Geant4 EM physics in terms of backscattering.

731 Figure 16 shows the results concerning the test calculating the backscattering coefficient
732 for 30, 60 and 90 keV electrons, incident normally on the target, compared against the
733 experimental measurements of the project Exacrad of the European Space Agency.

734 It is possible to observe that with Geant4 11.1 there is an improvement in the agreement
735 between the simulation results obtained with the EM constructor *Opt3* and the experimental
736 data, for the gold and bismuth targets (high-Z targets). This improvement is ascribed to
737 the revision of the multiple scattering parameters for this EM constructor (see Table 5).
738 *Livermore*, *Opt4* and *Penelope* exhibit a similar overall agreement with the reference data,
739 attributed to their adoption of the same multiple scattering model and parameters (see
740 Tables 4 and 5). For these constructors there is no significant difference between Geant4
741 10.5 and 11.1.

Figure 14: Exemplary electron backscattering coefficients calculated for Al, Ta and U targets, for different angles of incidence, compared against the Sandia Lab experimental data (Lockwood et al. ^{85, 86}).

Figure 15: Mean Relative Error (MRE) calculated for Be, C, Al, Ti, Mo, Ta and U targets, compared against the Sandia Lab experimental data (Lockwood et al. ⁸⁵, ⁸⁶). The MRE are calculated over the incident angles and electron energies under study.

Figure 16: Top: Electron backscattering coefficients calculated for 30, 60 and 90 keV electrons, incident on Au, Bi and Si targets. The reference data are experimental measurements of the project Exacrad of the European Space Agency. Middle: ratio of the electron backscattering coefficients calculated by means of Geant4 10.5 and 11.1 and the experimental reference data. Bottom: Mean Relative Error (MRE), calculated for each EM physics constructor under study.

742 IV.E.2. 13 MeV electron forward scatter from foils

743 This test, documented in detail in Arce et al.¹, is an experimental benchmark of the scatter
744 of electrons with energy equal to 13 MeV, for a comprehensive set of scattering materials
745 (Be, C, Al, Ti, Cu, Ta, Au), for thicknesses that result in a characteristic angle (or root
746 mean square scattering angle) of 2–8° (Faddegon et al.²⁰, Ross et al.⁸⁷, Vilches et al.⁸⁸).
747 The test is of particular interest for the benchmarking of Geant4 for electron therapy when
748 using medical linear accelerators with thin targets intended to minimize electron energy loss
749 and the generation of x-rays.

750 The 13 MeV electron beam has an experimental energy spread that is sufficiently small
751 to consider it mono-energetic. The beam has a Gaussian circular spot of 0.1 cm FWHM
752 and is normally incident on the exit window, a scattering foil of different thicknesses and
753 compositions, a monitor chamber, and mylar slabs on either side of a region filled with
754 helium. The scoring plane is perpendicular to the beam axis and is located 1.182 m from
755 the exit window. The fluence of electrons is scored in radial spatial bins of 1 mm width.

756 Figure 17 shows the results of the test. It can be observed that the results obtained
757 with Geant4 physics lists *Opt4*, *Livermore* and *Penelope* do not change from Geant4 10.5 to
758 11.1, while *Opt3* produces larger differences against the reference data for Geant4 11.1. The
759 bottom plot of Figure 17 shows the ratio of the simulation and experimental data for Geant4
760 11.2.1 and it is possible to observe that the agreement with experimental data improves again
761 for this version of Geant4 and this is due to the changes in the multiple scattering parameters
762 of the Geant4 EM constructor *Opt3*. These results are consistent with the findings of the
763 electron FLASH radiotherapy test (see Section IV.D.).

Figure 17: Top: Fluence of forward-scattered electrons obtained with a 13 MeV electron beam incident on the following foils: 0.926 g/cm² Be, 0.546 g/cm² C, 0.14 g/cm² Al, 0.0910 g/cm² Ti, 0.0864 g/cm² Cu, 0.443 g/cm² Ta, and 0.0312 g/cm² Au. Middle: ratio of the fluences of the forward-scattered electrons, plotted against the lateral position, for the different foils, for Geant4 10.5 and 11.1. Bottom: ratio of the fluences of the forward-scattered electrons, for *Opt3* with Geant4 versions 11.1 and 11.2.1. The shadowed areas indicate the experimental uncertainties.

764 IV.E.3. Test on bremsstrahlung from thick targets

765 This test focuses on the capability of Geant4 to model bremsstrahlung radiation produced
766 by thick targets of Al and Pb, particularly important when modelling X-ray beams from
767 linacs used in radiotherapy. Here, a brief description of the test is provided. The reader can
768 refer to Arce et al.¹ for more details.

769 A mono-energetic electron beam with a diameter of 0.35 cm and energy 15.18 MeV is
770 normally incident with constant fluence on a titanium exit window, followed by a silicon
771 transmission current monitor, and, finally, a pure target encased in a steel target chamber.
772 The photon fluence is scored on the surface of several concentric spherical rings in a sphere
773 of 1 m radius centered at the intersection of the beam axis with the upstream face of the
774 target. A global production cut of 0.01 mm is adopted. The simulation results are compared
775 to experiment; data documented in Faddegon et al.^{89,90}.

776 The results of this test were first reported in Arce et al.¹ for Geant4 10.5. Nevertheless,
777 in that release, Geant4 did not propagate the statistical weight correctly and the results
778 shown used a local version of Geant4 10.5 where this problem was fixed. The problem was
779 then fixed in the kernel of Geant4 in later releases of the Monte Carlo Toolkit and, here, we
780 report the new results obtained with the test for Geant4 11.1.

781 The top plot of Figure 18 shows the bremsstrahlung spectra obtained with Geant4 11.1.
782 The bottom plot shows the ratios of the simulation results to the reference experimental
783 measurements. For photon energies larger than 0.4 MeV, the ratio is close to unity. For
784 lower energies, there are significant differences between simulation results and experimental
785 data, especially for lead.

Figure 18: Top: Bremsstrahlung spectra obtained with a 15.18 MeV electron beam incident on targets of Al and Pb. Bottom: ratio of the simulation results to the experimental reference data.

786 IV.E.4. Fano Cavity test

787 The Fano cavity test is designed to check the accuracy of the condensed history (CH) electron
788 transport when simulating the response of detectors with gaseous cavities. In particular, the
789 different factors involved in the electron transport, i.e., the step limitation, effects of energy
790 loss, modelling of multiple Coulomb scattering, are tested using the Fano cavity principle
791 (Fano⁹¹). This test is recommended by the AAPM Research Committee Task Group 268⁹².

792 A beam of 1.25 MeV gamma rays traverses an ionization chamber, which consists of
793 a cylinder made of 5 mm water (G4_WATER) walls and a 2 mm cavity filled with steam
794 (G4_WATER with a density of 1.0 mg/cm³) (Poon et al.⁹³). The direction of the photon
795 beam is along the cylinder axis and there is particle equilibrium in the ionization chamber.
796 With this set-up, the ratio of the dose deposited divided by the beam energy fluence should
797 be equal to the mass-energy transfer coefficient of the wall material.

798 As explained in Arce et al.¹, this test requires specific physics modelling conditions, and
799 the physics constructors used in this test (indicated with a * for clarity) are not identical
800 to the corresponding Geant4 EM physics constructors except the modelling of the electron
801 Coulomb scattering and the corresponding stepping algorithm. The EM physics constructors
802 under study are *Opt3** and *Opt4**. *Livermore* and *Penelope* are not considered as they have
803 the same multiple scattering model of *Opt4*.

804 Figure 19 shows the dose ratio calculated with the simulation and the theoretical value,
805 varying the *dRoverRange*, which is a parameter of the Geant4 multiple scattering. While
806 the results obtained with *Opt4** do not change from Geant4 10.5 and 11.1, those with *Opt3**
807 vary, but, still, the agreement with unity is within 1%.

Figure 19: Ratio of simulated dose and the theoretical value plotted against the *dRoverRange* parameter.

V. Nuclear fragmentation cross sections benchmarking tests

Three independent tests are included in the G4–Med benchmarking suite to evaluate the total hadronic inelastic cross section, which is described with the Glauber–Gribov model in Geant4 (Geant4 Collaboration⁶³), and three different nuclear fragmentation models available in Geant4, the Binary Light Ion Cascade (BIC), the Quantum Molecular Dynamics (QMD) and the Liege Cascade (INCL) models (Arce et al.¹), describing the final state of the fragmentation process.

The BIC models nuclear fragmentation in the energy range between 0 and 6 GeV/u, by describing the interaction between the projectile and the participating nucleons of the target nucleus (Arce et al.¹). The residual nucleus is in pre-equilibrium state and is de-excited to the equilibrium state using the pre-compound model (Geant4 Collaboration⁶³). The final de-excitation is performed by the Geant4 de-excitation module. It invokes the Fermi Break–Up, neutron and light ion evaporation, fission for heavy fragment emission, GEM model for light fragment emission, and photon evaporation to model the nuclear gamma cascade (Geant4 Collaboration⁶³). A significant change between Geant4 10.5 and 11.1 is in the modelling of the de-excitation channels in the Fermi Break–Up model. Many more reaction channels are considered in Geant4 11.1 (from 991 to 5421 reactions) (Ungaro⁹⁴).

The QMD models ion nuclear fragmentation between 100 MeV/u and 10 GeV/u. Below 100 MeV/u, the BIC is used. The QMD describes the interaction between the projectile and all the nucleons of the target nucleus (Arce et al.¹).

The INCL models the fragmentation model and all the subsequent processes, including nuclear de-excitation, in the energy range between 0 and 3 GeV/u. The target nucleons are treated as a free Fermi gas in a static potential well, whereas the projectile is modeled without Fermi motion (Arce et al.¹).

Above the limit of applicability of the BIC, QMD and INCL, the Fritiof parton string model (Geant4 Collaboration⁶³) is adopted, nevertheless, it is not tested in this work as the energy range is too high for bio–medical applications.

836 V.A. Regression testing results

837 V.A.1. Test of nucleus–nucleus hadronic inelastic scattering cross sections

838 This test, described in detail in Arce et al.¹, calculates the total cross section of hadron–
839 nucleus and nucleus–nucleus collisions, which is then compared to reference experimental
840 measurements of the Experimental Nuclear Reaction Data (EXFOR) database (Zerkin and
841 Pritychenko⁹⁵).

842 The total inelastic scattering hadronic cross sections are calculated for incident protons
843 and carbon nuclei, for the following reactions: $p+{}^{12}_6\text{C}$, $p+{}^{16}_8\text{O}$, $p+{}^{27}_{13}\text{Al}$, $p+{}^{40}_{20}\text{Ca}$, ${}^{12}_6\text{C}+{}^{12}_6\text{C}$,
844 and ${}^{12}_6\text{C}+{}^{27}_{13}\text{Al}$. In Geant4, the total inelastic scattering hadronic cross section is based
845 on the Glauber representation with the Gribov screening correction on inelastic screening
846 (Kopeliovich⁹⁶, Fesefeldt⁹⁷, Grichine^{98,99}) and it is used in all the Geant4 hadronic physics
847 constructors.

848 Figure 20 shows the results of the regression testing between Geant4 10.5 and 11.1. The
849 total inelastic cross sections is plotted as a function of the kinetic energy of the projectile
850 and is compared to the experimental data of the EXFOR database. Both releases of Geant4
851 provide the same level of agreement with the reference data, for both incident protons and
852 carbon ions. Figure 21 shows the total inelastic cross section in the energy range between 1
853 MeV/u and 100 MeV/u. It is possible to observe that for incident protons, the cross section
854 is lower up to 10 MeV in the case of Geant4 11.1, while there is no difference for incident
855 carbon nuclei.

Figure 20: Total inelastic cross sections for the nuclear reactions under study.

Figure 21: Total inelastic cross section zoomed in the energy range between 1 MeV/u and 100 MeV/u, together with the ratios of the cross sections calculated with Geant4 11.1 and 10.5.

856 V.A.2. 62 MeV/u ^{12}C fragmentation test

857 This test, described in detail in Arce et al.¹, calculates the double-differential cross sections
858 of light fragment production of 62 MeV/u ^{12}C ions incident on a thin natural carbon target.
859 The secondary fragments under investigation are ^1H , ^2H , ^3H , ^4He , ^6Li , ^7Li , ^7Be , ^9Be , ^{10}B
860 and ^{11}B . The calculated cross sections are compared to experimental measurements reported
861 in Napoli et al.¹⁰⁰. Simulations are executed modelling the nuclear fragmentation with the
862 Binary Light Ions Cascade (BIC) (Folger et al.¹⁰¹) and the Liege Intranuclear Cascade
863 (INCL) (Boudard et al.¹⁰², Mancusi et al.¹⁰³). The Quantum Molecular Dynamics (QMD)
864 (Koi¹⁰⁴) is not subject of the test, as, below 100 MeV/u, its Geant4 physics constructor
865 (*G4IonQMDPhysics*) switches to the BIC (Arce et al.¹).

866 The regression testing shows that the cross section of production of H isotopes does not
867 change between Geant4 10.5 and 11.1, while there are some differences for ^4He , ^6Li , ^7Li , ^7Be ,
868 ^9Be , ^{10}B and ^{11}B , for both INCL and BIC fragmentation models. Nevertheless, the overall
869 agreement against experimental data does not change significantly between Geant4 10.5 and
870 11.1. Figures 22 and 23 show as exemplary case the double differential cross section of
871 production of ^{10}B and its ratio against the reference data, respectively. In this case, the
872 differential double cross-section is slightly higher in Geant4 11.1 than in Geant4 10.5.

Figure 22: ^{10}B production double-differential cross sections, calculated with Geant4 10.5 and 11.1. Reference experimental measurements from Napoli et al. ¹⁰⁰.

Figure 23: Ratio of the simulation and reference data for ^{10}B production double-differential cross sections. Reference experimental measurements from Napoli et al. ¹⁰⁰.

873 **V.A.3. 300 MeV/u ^{12}C ion charge-changing cross section test**

874 This test, described in detail in Arce et al.¹, benchmarks the partial and total charge-
875 changing cross sections of ^{12}C ions with energy 300 MeV/u as simulated by Geant4 against
876 experimental data published in Toshito et al.²⁵, obtained with an emulsion plate in the NIRS
877 P152 experiment.

878 Figure 24 shows the results of the regression testing between Geant4 version 10.5 and
879 11.1. The bottom plot shows the ratio of the simulation and reference data. The agreement
880 within the experimental uncertainty is confirmed for the total cross section and Li partial
881 cross section when using Geant4 version 11.1. In the case of the Be partial cross section,
882 Geant4 11.1 provides poorer agreement than 10.5 with respect to the experimental mea-
883 surements. Depending on the specific fragmentation model, a degradation of the level of
884 agreement of approximately 10-15% has been found. However, in Geant4 11.1 the calcula-
885 tion of the Boron partial cross section improves significantly, especially for the BIC model,
886 for which an agreement within the experimental uncertainty is found. In the case of QMD
887 and INCL, the difference to the reference data decreases to below 20%. Overall, in this test,
888 when compared to INCL and QMD, BIC and BIC_HP provide a better agreement against
889 reference data.

Figure 24: Top: Comparison of Geant4 simulation results obtained with Geant4 10.5 and 11.1 against experimental data (Toshito et al. ²⁵) for ^{12}C total and partial charge-changing cross sections. The energy of the incident ^{12}C ion beam is 300 MeV/u. Bottom: Ratio of simulated and reference data for Geant4 10.5 and 11.1.

890 VI. Electromagnetic and hadronic physics benchmark- 891 ing tests

892 This section reports the results of the G4–Med tests where both electromagnetic and hadronic
893 physics processes are objects of the testing. Section VI.A. briefly describes the physics lists
894 of Geant4 benchmarked in this work and summarises the evolution of the Geant4 hadronic
895 physics from Geant4 10.5 to 11.1, of interest for bio–medical physics applications. Sec-
896 tion VI.B. shows new developments of the *Hadrontherapy* test in terms of experimental mi-
897 crodosimetry. Section VI.C. describes a new test introduced in the G4–Med benchmarking
898 system for in–vivo PET for heavy ions. Finally, Section VI.D. reports significance results of
899 the regression testing of existing tests, documented in Arce et al.¹ performed with Geant4
900 10.5 and 11.1.

901 VI.A. Evolution of the Geant4 hadronic physics from Geant4 10.5 902 to 11.1, of interest for bio–medical applications

903 The Geant4 physics lists, modelling both EM and hadronic physics interactions, subject
904 of the benchmarking of Geant4 for hadrontherapy are *QGSP_BIC_HP*, *QGSP_BIC_AllHP*,
905 *QGSP_BERT_HP*, *QGSP_INCLXX_HP*, and *Shielding*, and they are briefly described in
906 Table 7.

907 From Geant4 version 10.5 to 11.1 there have been limited changes in the hadronic physics
908 models relevant for bio–medical applications, in the hadronic inelastic cross sections and
909 physics lists used in this benchmark. Consistency improvements, clean–up and optimization
910 of the code have been performed, but without reported relevant impact in the situations of
911 interest in this study.

912 New versions of the hadronic data sets are used in Geant4 11.1. First of all, the new
913 dataset G4NDL.4.7, for data driven models for neutron transport, is used in the “*_HP*”
914 physics lists. With respect to G4NDL.4.5 (present in Geant4 10.5), the new dataset incorpo-
915 rates new neutron cross–sections and final states obtained from JEFF–3.3 data library, and
916 includes new materials for the simulation of thermal neutrons. The dataset G4TENDL.1.4,
917 used by the “*_AllHP*” physics lists, was released with Geant4 version 11.0 and uses ENDF/B–
918 VIII.0 and TENDL–2019 libraries (vs. G4TENDL.1.3.2 present in Geant4 version 10.5,

919 which used ENDF/B–VII.1 and TENDL–2014 libraries).

920 With respect to G4PARTICLEXS.1.1 present in Geant4 10.5, the G4PARTICLEXS.4.0
921 dataset present in Geant4 11.1 was derived using cross–section data from G4NDL.4.7 for
922 neutrons with energies below 20 MeV, from G4TENDL.1.4 for protons below 150 MeV and
923 light ions at selected energy ranges, and from new data for gamma–nuclear cross sections
924 below 130 MeV. This dataset is used in all non-HP pre-compiled Physics Lists⁶³. For gamma–
925 nuclear cross section, the old cross section class *G4PhotoNuclearCrossSection* is used above
926 130 MeV.

927 G4ENSDFSTATE.2.3, released with Geant4 version 10.7, incorporates minor changes
928 in nuclear levels and isomer lifetimes vs. G4ENSDFSTATE.2.2 present in Geant4 10.5.
929 After dedicated efforts, G4ENSDFSTATE.2.3 is coherent with G4PhotonEvaporation.5.7
930 and G4RadioactiveDecay.5.6 datasets.

931 G4PhotonEvaporation.5.7, released with Geant4 version 10.7, updates data on nuclear
932 levels and transition probabilities vs. G4PhotonEvaporation.5.3 in Geant4 10.5. These
933 data are used in the Geant4 nuclear de–excitation module used in the physics list con-
934 taining “*BIC*”, “*INCLXX*” or “*QMD*” in its name, as well as in “*AllHP*” physics lists.
935 G4RadioactiveDecay.5.6, released with Geant4 version 10.7, incorporates various updates,
936 additions, and fixes with respect to G4RadioactiveDecay.5.3, present in Geant4 10.5. The
937 radioactive decay module is used by default in the physics list *Shielding* and those including
938 “*HP*” or “*AllHP*” in its name.

Geant4 physics list	QGSP_BIC_HP	QGSP_BIC_AUHP	QGSP_BERT_HP	QGSP_INCLXX_HP	Shielding
<i>EM physics</i>	<i>Opt4</i>				
	<i>G4EmStandardPhysics</i>				
<i>Radioactive decay</i>	Modelling Synchrotron radiation and gamma/e-/e+ nuclear processes <i>G4EmExtraPhysics</i> <i>G4RadioactiveDecayPhysics</i>				
<i>Hadron elastic scattering</i>	Modelling of rare decays of hadrons (pion, kaons, etc), not relevant for the G4-Med tests <i>G4HadronElasticPhysicsHP</i>				
<i>Other hadronic physics processes</i>	<i>G4HadronPhysics</i> <i>QGSP_BIC_HP*</i>	<i>G4HadronPhysics</i> <i>QGSP_BIC_AUHP*</i>	<i>G4HadronPhysics</i> <i>QGSP_BERT_HP*</i>	<i>G4HadronPhysics</i> <i>INCLXX</i>	<i>G4HadronPhysics</i> <i>Shielding</i> <i>BERT_HP* < 3GeV,</i> <i>FTPF_HP* > 3GeV,</i> <i>G4IonElasticPhysics</i>
<i>Ion elastic physics</i>	<i>G4IonElasticPhysics</i>				
<i>Other ion physics</i>	<i>G4IonPhysics</i> (<i>G4BinaryLightIonReaction</i>)	<i>G4IonPhysicsPHP</i> (<i>G4ParticleHPInelastic < 200 MeV,</i> <i>G4BinaryLightIonReaction above</i>)	<i>G4IonPhysics</i> (<i>G4BinaryLightIonReaction</i>)	<i>G4IonINCLXXPhysics</i>	<i>G4IonQMDPhysics</i>

Table 7: Geant4 physics models of the hadronic physics list used in this paper; *_HP: use of evaluated data bases only for neutrons; *_allHP=use of evaluated data bases for n,p,d,t,³He and alpha particles.

939 VI.B. Hadrontherapy test

940 The *Hadrontherapy* test is released in Geant4 as an advanced example (called *Hadrontherapy*)
941 since 2003. The test has been included in the G4–Med benchmarking system since its first
942 release in 2019. It was originally focused on comparing clonogenic cells’ Survival Fraction
943 (SF) curves with experimental radiobiological data (see Arce et al. ¹). The regression testing
944 between Geant4 10.5 and 11.1 of the calculation of the SF curve did not report any change
945 between the two releases of Geant4, therefore the results will not be shown here.

946 An additional functionality has been recently included in the test, focused on the cal-
947 culation of track–averaged LET (\bar{L}_T) curves and their comparison against experimental mi-
948 crodosimetric data, obtained at the CATANA facility, Laboratori Nazionali del Sud, Istituto
949 Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare in Catania (INFN–LNS, Italy).

950 VI.B.1. Simulation set-up

951 The CATANA protontherapy clinical beamline, installed at LNS–INFN, is modelled in de-
952 tail in terms of materials and geometry. A voxelized water phantom is set at the end of the
953 beamline, to replicate a standard water tank, conventionally adopted in a clinical environ-
954 ment, for depth dose curve reconstruction. For this test, the tank is segmented into slices
955 with size $400 \times 400 \times 0.01 \text{ mm}^3$.

956 The proton beam is simulated with a Gaussian energy distribution, centered at a nominal
957 energy of 62.40 MeV and a standard deviation of 0.25 MeV. The beam spot is modelled as
958 circular, following a bivariate Gaussian distribution with a standard deviation of 5 mm.
959 A Gaussian angular distribution is assumed for the beam, with a standard deviation of
960 0.028 degrees. Proton beam energy modulation is achieved using a plastic modulator wheel,
961 generating a modulation width of 11 mm in water and a maximum proton range of 30 mm
962 in water. Each simulation execution comprises a total of 3.6×10^6 histories. The production
963 cut for secondary electrons, defining the threshold below which secondary particles are not
964 individually generated and tracked, is set equal to 0.1 mm.

965 The track–averaged LET, \bar{L}_T , is computed using *QGSP_BIC_HP*, *QGSP_BERT_HP*,
966 and *QGSP_BIC_AllHP*⁶³, and compared against y_F values defined in the ICRU Report 36¹⁰⁵,
967 derived from experimental microdosimetric spectra acquired at thirteen different depths in

968 water. These spectra were obtained using the MicroPlus probe detector (Tran et al.¹⁰⁶)
 969 developed at the Centre For Medical and Radiation Physics, University of Wollongong,
 970 Australia(Tran et al.¹⁰⁶).

971 The term *averaged LET* refers to the mean value of the restricted electronic stopping
 972 power when considering all particles traversing a specific volume within a radiation field.

973 The track-averaged LET (\bar{L}_T) is calculated as described by Petringa et al.¹⁶, with an
 974 approach analogous to the method C suggested by Cortés-Giraldo and Carabe¹⁰⁷ to avoid
 975 biased results:

$$976 \quad \bar{L}_T = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n [\sum_{i=1}^N L_i l_i]_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n [\sum_{i=1}^N l_i]_j}, \quad (7)$$

977 where l represents the track length of a particle in the given volume. L_i is the electronic
 978 stopping power obtained from Geant4 look-up tables. The index i iterates over the total
 979 number of steps N taken by a specific particle within the considered volume, while the index
 980 j iterates over all primary and secondary particles travelling within that volume.

981 VI.B.2. Results

982 Figure 25 shows the comparison of the track-averaged LET curve (\bar{L}_T), obtained with
 983 *QGSP_BIC_HP*, *QGSP_BERT_HP* and *QGSP_BIC_AllHP*. The simulation results are com-
 984 pared to the reference y_F values. It is possible to observe that the Geant4 simulations agree
 985 within 15% with the reference data. There is no significant difference among the three
 986 Geant4 physics lists studied.

Figure 25: \bar{L}_T curves obtained with Geant4 11.1, when using *QGSP_BIC_HP* (red), *QGSP_BERT_HP* (orange) and *QGSP_BIC_AllHP* (blue), against y_F values obtained experimentally (Petringa et al.¹⁶).

987 VI.C. In-vivo PET test for carbon and oxygen ion therapy

988 This test has been introduced in the G4-Med benchmarking system relatively recently and is
 989 documented in Chacon et al.²⁷ and Chacon et al.²⁸. It quantitatively assesses the capability
 990 of Geant4 in predicting positron-emitting fragment production using three hadronic inelastic
 991 fragmentation models: BIC, QMD and INCL.

992 Experimental data of the absolute yields of positron-emitting fragments (¹⁰C, ¹¹C, and
 993 ¹⁵O), generated during the irradiation of gelatin, PMMA, and polyethylene block phantoms
 994 with ¹²C and ¹⁶O ion beams, serve as reference data. These beams, with energies equal
 995 to 148.5, 290.5, and 350 MeV/u for ¹²C and 148 and 290 MeV/u for ¹⁶O, were measured
 996 using the OpenPET scanner at HIMAC, Japan, as detailed in Chacon et al.²⁷ and Akamatsu
 997 et al.¹⁰⁸.

998 The focus is on the comprehensive comparison of simulated positron yields against
 999 experimental measurements across three key regions: entrance, build-up and Bragg peak,
 1000 and tail regions.

1001 The experimental set-up, described in Chacon et al.²⁷, involves irradiating phantoms
 1002 made of PMMA, polyethylene, or gelatin, using monoenergetic carbon and oxygen ion beams
 1003 as listed in Table 8. Positron annihilation profiles were acquired using a DOI-PET scanner
 1004 prototype from QST (Akamatsu et al.¹⁰⁸), with subsequent decomposition into contributions
 1005 from ¹¹C, ¹⁰C, and ¹⁵O by fitting the time activity curve, voxel by voxel, at the end of the
 1006 irradiation period. The profile is taken using the full width at tenth maximum of the beam,
 1007 parallel to the path of the beam in the phantom.

Incident ion	Energy (MeV/u)	σ_x (mm)	σ_y (mm)	Beam flux (pps)
¹² C	148.5	2.77	2.67	$1.8 \times 10^9 \pm 3.8 \times 10^7$
¹² C	290.5	3.08	4.70	$1.8 \times 10^9 \pm 6.4 \times 10^7$
¹² C	350	2.50	2.98	$1.8 \times 10^9 \pm 4.6 \times 10^7$
¹⁶ O	148	2.79	2.89	$1.1 \times 10^9 \pm 2.8 \times 10^7$
¹⁶ O	290	2.60	4.90	$1.1 \times 10^9 \pm 7.0 \times 10^7$

Table 8: Beam parameters for each ion species and energy. All beams had an energy spread of 0.2 % of the nominal energy; 95% confidence intervals are listed for beam flux.

1008 VI.C.1. Simulation set-up

1009 The *in-vivo* PET test models the experimental setup as accurately as possible. The selection
1010 of physics models followed the configurations specified in the Geant4 advanced hadrontherapy
1011 example. The physics lists is *QGSP_BIC_HP* with *Opt3* as EM physics constructor. The
1012 nuclear fragmentation model is modeled with BIC, QMD and INCL. The heavy ion beams
1013 are modeled as two-dimensional Gaussian pencil beams, with same sigmas (σ) as observed
1014 experimentally and detailed in Table 8. An air gap of 1.75 meters separates the beam's
1015 origin from the phantom's surface to replicate the experimental conditions as accurately
1016 as possible. Phantoms, constructed in dimensions of $100 \times 100 \times 300$ mm³, are composed of
1017 either polyethylene, polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), or gelatin housed in an open-top
1018 PMMA container. The gelatin phantom features a 4 mm wall thickness and is filled with
1019 water. All material properties are defined based on the NIST definitions.

1020 Each simulation configuration is executed with 2×10^7 histories. The identification of
1021 positron-emitting fragments is done tracing the origins of annihilating positrons. The spatial
1022 and temporal coordinates, alongside the parent ID of each positron annihilation, is recorded
1023 with a spatial resolution of 1.5 mm³ across the entire phantom, reflecting the capabilities of
1024 the OpenPET system for image reconstruction. A Gaussian filter, characterized by a 2.6 mm
1025 full-width at half-maximum (FWHM), is applied to emulate the point spread function of the
1026 PET imaging system. Line profiles, extracted at the full width at tenth maximum (FWTM)
1027 of each beam, traverses the phantom along the beam path. These profiles are normalised to
1028 the number of incident particles simulated. Data are grouped into 20 batches for statistical
1029 analysis, with the calculation of mean and standard deviation for each. This approach yields
1030 a statistical confidence level of 10% in the mean/standard deviation across the majority of
1031 the beam's trajectory.

1032 The results are analysed in three regions, entrance, Bragg Peak and tail. The entrance
1033 and the Bragg Peak regions are separated by the proximal edge in the z dimension (along the
1034 path of the beam), defined as the first point at which the dose deposited along the central
1035 axis exceeds the entrance plateau dose by more than 5% of the difference between peak dose
1036 and the entrance plateau dose. The Bragg Peak and the tail regions are separated by the
1037 distal edge in z , defined as the last point at which the deposited dose is greater than 5% of
1038 the absolute peak dose value. The simulations are performed with Geant4 11.1.

1039 VI.C.2. Results and Discussion

1040 Figures 26, 27 and 28 show the positron emission yield for the incident ^{12}C and ^{16}O ion beams
 1041 in the gelatine, PMMA and polyethylene phantoms, respectively, calculated with Geant4
 1042 11.1. The plots have inserts showing the ratio of the Geant4 simulated and experimental
 data.

1043 Figure 26: Top row: Positron yield per incident ^{12}C ion, with energy 148.5 MeV/u (left),
 290.5 MeV/u (middle), 350 MeV/u (right). Bottom row: ^{16}O ion, with energy 148 MeV/u
 1044 (left) and 290 MeV/u (right). The positron yield is plotted with respect to the depth in
 1045 the gelatin phantom. The yellow areas indicate the Bragg Peak regions. The bottom plots
 1046 in each row show the ratio between simulated and experimental data. The uncertainty of
 the ratio is shown as a shade around the curve. Experimental measurements from Chacon
 et al. ²⁷.

1044 Table 9 reports the results of the regression testing performed between Geant4 10.5 and
 1045 11.1 in terms of MRE and NMAE to identify the Geant4 fragmentation model that better
 1046 describes the experimental data considered in this test.

1047 The results, including the MRE and NMAE analysis, show that the INCL has the least
 1048 agreement against the experimental measurements. The BIC provides an overall better
 1049 agreement for the entrance and Bragg Peak region, while the QMD outperforms the BIC in
 1050 the distal region (tail).

Figure 27: Top row: Positron yield per incident ^{12}C ion, with energy 148.5 MeV/u (left), 290.5 MeV/u (middle), 350 MeV/u (right). Bottom row: ^{16}O ion, with energy 148 MeV/u (left) and 290 MeV/u (right). The positron yield is plotted with respect to the depth in the PMMA phantom. The yellow areas indicate the Bragg Peak regions. The bottom plots in each row show the ratio between simulated and experimental data. The uncertainty of the ratio is shown as a shade around the curve. Experimental measurements from Chacon et al. ²⁷.

Figure 28: Top row: Positron yield per incident ^{12}C ion, with energy 148.5 MeV/u (left), 290.5 MeV/u (middle), 350 MeV/u (right). Bottom row: ^{16}O ion, with energy 148 MeV/u (left) and 290 MeV/u (right). The positron yield is plotted with respect to the depth in the polyethylene phantom. The yellow areas indicate the Bragg Peak regions. The bottom plots in each row show the ratio between simulated and experimental data. The uncertainty of the ratio is shown as a shade around the curve. Experimental measurements from Chacon et al. ²⁷.

Target material	Particle	Energy (MeV/u)	Entrance	Build-up and Bragg peak	Tail region
Gelatin	^{12}C	148.	QMD	QMD/BIC	QMD
	^{12}C	290.	QMD	QMD	QMD
	^{12}C	350.	BIC	BIC	QMD
	^{16}O	148.	QMD	QMD/BIC	QMD
	^{16}O	290.	BIC	BIC	QMD
PMMA	^{12}C	148.	BIC	BIC	QMD
	^{12}C	290.	BIC	BIC	QMD
	^{12}C	350.	BIC	BIC	QMD
	^{16}O	148.	BIC	QMD	QMD
	^{16}O	290.	BIC	QMD/BIC	QMD
Polyethylene	^{12}C	148.	BIC	QMD/BIC	QMD
	^{12}C	290.	BIC	BIC	QMD
	^{12}C	350.	QMD/BIC	QMD/BIC	QMD
	^{16}O	148.	BIC	BIC	QMD
	^{16}O	290.	BIC	BIC	QMD

Table 9: Best Geant4 fragmentation model to describe the experimental positron yields for the different target materials and particle beams under study. The agreement is evaluated in terms of MRE and NMAE (see Section II.).

VI.D. Regression testing results

VI.D.1. 67.5 MeV proton Bragg Peak in water

This test, documented in detail in Arce et al.¹ and in Faddegon et al.²⁹, calculates the Bragg Peak in water of protons of mean energy 67.5 MeV and a gaussian energy spread of 0.4 MeV. The beam is incident on a water phantom, after traversing a tantalum (Ta) foil of either 101.6 μm or 381 μm thickness.

The physics list includes one of the EM constructors, *Livermore*, *Penelope*, *Opt3* or *Opt4*, coupled with hadronic physics, which is modelled by means of *QGSP_BIC_HP* (Arce et al.¹, Testa et al.¹⁰⁹).

The simulation results are compared to experimental measurements documented in Faddegon et al.²⁹, in terms of range R_{80} (corresponding to the 80% Bragg peak distal fall-off), and spread σ of a Gaussian describing the width of the Bragg peak as defined in Bortfeld¹¹⁰.

Figure 29 shows the R_{80} and the spread σ . It can be observed that, while there is no difference between the two releases of Geant4 in terms of R_{80} , there is a slight improvement in Geant4 11.1 in terms of spread σ , which maybe be due to the ICRU90 adoption to calculate the low energy proton stopping powers in water in Geant4 11.1.

Figure 29: Comparison of R_{80} and spread σ between Geant4 10.5/11.1 predictions and reference data, for a 67.5 MeV proton beam incident on a water phantom. The grey areas indicate the uncertainty affecting the experimental data. Reference data from Faddegon et al.²⁹.

VI.D.2. Light ion Bragg Peak curves

This test, documented in detail in Arce et al.¹, is aimed to compare R_{82} (range of heavy ions at 82% dose fall-off) in water, between Geant4 and experimental measurements performed at

1070 GSI (Schardt et al. ¹¹¹), for proton and ^{12}C beams with energies of interest for hadron therapy
 1071 (beam ranges are below 30 cm in water). The EM physics constructors under investigation
 1072 are *Opt3*, *Opt4*, *Livermore* and *Penelope*, while the hadronic physics component is defined,
 1073 for all the simulations, with *QGSP_BIC_HP*, similarly to what done in Arce et al. ¹.

1074 Figure 31 reports the differences of R_{82} between Geant4 calculations and experimental
 1075 measurements, for incident protons and ^{12}C ions. Taking into account the uncertainties
 1076 affecting the results, it is possible to observed a general improvement in the calculation of
 1077 the position of the Bragg Peak of approximately 0.2 mm for incident protons in Geant4 11.1.
 1078 In the case of incident carbon ions, Geant4 11.1 predicts more accurately the position of the
 1079 Bragg Peak up to 250 MeV/u incident energy. For higher energies the absolute difference
 1080 with the experimental data is approximately the same for Geant4 10.5 and 11.1. While
 1081 Geant4 10.5 tends to underestimate the position of R_{82} , Geant4 11.1 overestimates it. In
 1082 the case of 400 MeV/u, the highest incident energy under study, the difference of R_{82} is
 1083 approximately 1 mm. There is no significant difference in the results due to the adoption
 1084 of *Livermore*, *Opt3*, *Opt4* and *Penelope* EM constructors, because the model of heavy ion
 ionisation model is the same in all these EM constructors.

1085 Figure 30: Difference of R_{82} between Geant4 simulations and reference data (Schardt et al. ¹¹¹). The differences are plotted against the energy of the incident particles (protons and ^{12}C).

1086 VI.D.3. Neutron yield with protons and ^{12}C ions in thick targets

1087 This test, described in detail in Arce et al.¹, calculates the neutron yield in thick targets,
 1088 produced by incident protons with energy 113 MeV and 256 MeV and 290 MeV/u ^{12}C
 1089 ions. The simulation results are compared to experimental measurements documented in
 1090 M. M. Meier and Amian¹¹², M. M. Meier and Moss¹¹³ for protons and from Satoh et al.¹¹⁴
 1091 for carbon ions interacting in water. Table 10 reports the radius, thickness and material of
 1092 each target bombarded with either protons or ^{12}C ions. The physics lists under study are
 1093 *QGSP_BIC_HP* and *Shielding*.

1094 The neutron yield per incident primary particle per steradian per energy (equally spaced
 1095 logarithmic energy intervals) is scored at specific angular bins; for proton beams, 7.5° , 30° ,
 1096 60° and 150° for 113 MeV and 30° , 60° , 120° and 150° for 256 MeV; 15° - 90° at 15° angular
 1097 steps for carbon ions.

Material	Radius (cm)	Thickness (cm)		Density (g/cm^3)	
		protons			
		113 MeV	256 MeV		
Aluminum	3.65	8.0	4.00	20.0	2.699
Carbon	3.65	8.0	5.83	30.0	1.867
Iron	3.65	8.0	1.57	8.0	7.867
		Carbon ions (290 MeV/u)			
G4.WATER	-	-		18.0	1.0

Table 10: Target dimensions, material and density for each proton energy and carbon ion beam configuration. Table from Arce et al.¹.

1098 The regression testing results do not report any difference between Geant4 10.5 and 11.1
 1099 in terms of neutron yield, for protons incident on Al and C targets. Instead, differences up to
 1100 20% between the two releases of Geant4 are observed in the calculation of the neutron yield
 1101 below 10 MeV neutron energy for a Fe target, when using *QGSP_BIC_HP*. In this specific
 1102 case, Geant4 11.1 produces slightly more neutrons and has less agreement than Geant4 10.5
 1103 with the reference data. The regression testing does not report any change in the results
 1104 when using the *Shielding* physics list. Finally, the test did not report any change in the
 1105 neutron production yield of 290 MeV/u ^{12}C ions in water between Geant4 10.5 and 11.1.

1106 This is the only test in the G4–Med suite that benchmarks Geant4 in terms of neutron
1107 production and the results of the regression testing show that more tests are needed to
1108 monitor neutron production (in addition to neutron physics).

Figure 31: Neutron yields produced by protons in a Fe thick target.

1109 VI.D.4. Fragmentation of a 400 MeV/u ^{12}C ion beam in water

1110 This test, published in Bolst et al.³⁰ and described in detail in Arce et al.¹, benchmarks
1111 Geant4's modelling of the fragmentation process against experimental measurements of a
1112 ^{12}C ion beam incident upon a water target performed at GSI (Haettner et al.¹¹⁵).

1113 A 400 MeV/u ^{12}C ion pencil beam, with an energy σ of 0.15% and a FWHM of 5 mm, is
1114 incident on a water phantom with different thicknesses (59 mm, 159 mm, 258 mm, 279 mm,
1115 288 mm, 312 mm and 347 mm). The physical quantities object of the benchmarking are the
1116 yield, angular and kinetic energy distributions of light fragments, from hydrogen to boron.

1117 The *QGSP_BIC_HP* physics list is used to model particle interactions. The Geant4
1118 EM constructor *Opt4* is adopted to model the electromagnetic interactions. The tests are
1119 performed changing the model of hadronic inelastic scattering of heavy ions: BIC, QMD and
1120 INCL.

1121 Figure 32 shows the fragment yield calculated with respect to the depth in water when
1122 using Geant4 10.5 and 11.1. It is possible to observe that BIC in Geant4 11.1 agrees better
1123 with the reference data for H, He and B fragment yields (see Figure 33). In addition to BIC,
1124 QMD and INCL have better agreement to the reference data in the case of B.

1125 Figure 34, left, shows the MRE of the kinetic and angular distributions, calculated for
1126 the light fragments, at different depths in the water medium, for both Geant4 10.5 and 11.1.
1127 The plots on the right of the same Figure report the MRE for the same physical quantities,
1128 calculated over the different positions in the water medium under study. It is possible to
1129 observe that, for both BIC and INCL, there is slightly less agreement in terms of angular
1130 distribution of the fragments with Geant4 11.1. Instead, there are no significant difference
1131 in terms of kinetic energy distributions.

(a) Fragment yield calculated with respect to depth. Experimental data from Haettner et al. ¹¹⁵.

Figure 32: Ratio of Geant4 simulation results and reference data in terms of fragment yields. Experimental data from Haettner et al. ¹¹⁵.

Figure 33: Mean Relative Error calculated for H (left), He (middle) and B (right), for the calculation of the fragments yields.

Figure 34: Left: Mean Relative Error (MRE) calculated for the angular (top) and kinetic energy (bottom) distributions of the light fragments, for both Geant4 10.5 and 11.1. Right: MRE calculated over the different positions in the water phantom under study.

1132 VII. Computing performance test

1133 The aim of this part of the project is to benchmark the execution times of the main Geant4
1134 physics constructors and lists used within the G4–Med suite. This is achieved using a
1135 simplified Geant4 simulation, described in Section VII.A..

1136 Each simulation configuration of the Geant4 application is executed in sequential mode
1137 (i.e. single threaded) on a dedicated computing server, a 2.30 GHz Intel Xeon E5–2650v3
1138 based machine maintained by the Centre for Medical and Radiation Physics, University of
1139 Wollongong, Australia. Each simulation configuration is repeated ten times with different
1140 random seeds. Then, the average and standard deviation of the execution times are calcu-
1141 lated. The computing performance ϵ is then calculated as $\epsilon = \frac{T}{T_{ref}}$, where T and T_{ref} are
1142 the execution times of the Geant4 simulation for a particular physics lists/constructor and
1143 a reference list/constructor, respectively.

1144 VII.A. Geant4 simulation set-up

1145 The Geant4 simulation consists of a 30 cm water cube, a pencil beam is generated at the
1146 centre of one of the face’s surface, just inside the water medium. No particle track information
1147 or other physical quantities (for example, energy deposition) are retrieved or stored. The
1148 simulation only generates primary particles with a defined energy and direction, and tracks
1149 them in the water phantom. The execution time from the start of the first event to the
1150 end of the last event is stored. This is to minimise the contribution to the computational
1151 time deriving from components other than the physics modelling, e.g. geometry operations,
1152 retrieval and storage of track and stepping information in Geant4 User Actions.

1153 VII.A.1. Electromagnetic settings

1154 Mono–energetic electron beams are generated to compare the execution times of both
1155 Geant4–DNA track structure (*Geant4-DNA-Opt2*, *Geant4-DNA-Opt4* and *Geant4-DNA-*
1156 *Opt6*) and Geant4 condensed history EM constructors (*Opt3*, *Opt4*, *Livermore* and *Pene-*
1157 *lope*).

1158 The energy of the primary electron beams are: 1, 10, 100, 10^3 , 10^4 keV. All the Geant4

1159 condensed history EM physics constructors have a cut of 1 μm and a threshold production
1160 of 1 keV, which corresponds to an electron range in water of $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$. The choice of a 1 keV
1161 production threshold is dictated by the fact that this is the minimum recommended energy
1162 of the Geant4 EM *Opt3* constructor.

1163 Simulations with the Geant4–DNA physics constructors are performed for primary en-
1164 ergies of 1 and 10 keV only, due to *Geant4-DNA-Opt4* and *Geant4-DNA-Opt6* having max-
1165 imum electron ionisation energies of 10 and 250 keV, respectively. Conversely, Geant4 con-
1166 densed history EM physics constructors are executed only for electron energies of 10 keV
1167 and higher due the adoption of the 1 keV cut.

1168 VII.A.2. Hadronic settings

1169 The execution times of the pre–built Geant4 physics lists for hadronic interactions are com-
1170 pared using a 150 MeV proton and a 290 MeV/u ^{12}C ion beam incident on the 30 cm
1171 water cube. In the case of the proton beam, the *QGSP_BIC_HP*, *QGSP_BIC_AUHP* and
1172 *QGSP_BERT_HP* physics lists are compared. In the case of an incident ^{12}C ion beam, the
1173 *QGSP_BIC_HP* is adopted. The ion fragmentation is modeled alternatively with BIC, QMD
1174 and INCL. *Opt4* is chosen in all the Geant4 physics lists under study to describe EM physics
1175 interactions, as it is deemed to be the most accurate for bio–medical applications.

1176 Both the proton and ^{12}C ion simulations are executed with a 0.1 mm and a 1 m cut.
1177 The 0.1 mm value represents a more clinically relevant description of the generation of
1178 delta electrons in the simulation. The 1 m cut has instead been chosen to minimize the
1179 contribution of the EM physics interactions (no generation of delta electrons), to compare
1180 the effect of different hadronic physics models in the execution times.

1181 VII.B. Results and Discussion

1182 Execution times for for Geant4–DNA and Geant4 condensed history EM physics construc-
1183 tors, for electron beams with energies 1 and 10 keV in water, are shown in Table 11. For 1
1184 keV electron beams, both *Geant4-DNA-Opt2* and *Geant4-DNA-Opt4* have similar execution
1185 times, while *Geant4-DNA-Opt6* is $\sim 15\%$ faster than the other two constructors. At 10 keV,
1186 *Geant4-DNA-Opt4* becomes significantly more computationally intensive than *Geant4-DNA-*

Energy (keV)	EM Physics constructor	Execution time per event (μs)	$\frac{G4EMconstructor}{Geant4-DNA-Opt2}$
1 keV	<i>Geant4-DNA-Opt2</i>	$(414. \pm 3.) \cdot 10$	1
	<i>Geant4-DNA-Opt4</i>	$(466. \pm 3.) \cdot 10$	1.12 ± 0.01
	<i>Geant4-DNA-Opt6</i>	$(353. \pm 2.) \cdot 10$	0.85 ± 0.01
10 keV	<i>Geant4-DNA-Opt2</i>	$(430. \pm 2.) \cdot 10^2$	1
	<i>Geant4-DNA-Opt4</i>	$(744. \pm 4.) \cdot 10^2$	1.73 ± 0.01
	<i>Geant4-DNA-Opt6</i>	$(357. \pm 4.) \cdot 10^2$	0.83 ± 0.01
	<i>Opt3</i>	$23. \pm 1.$	$(5.2 \pm 0.3) \cdot 10^{-4}$
	<i>Opt4</i>	$45. \pm 2.$	$(1.06 \pm 0.04) \cdot 10^{-3}$
	<i>Penelope</i>	$46. \pm 3.$	$(1.06 \pm 0.06) \cdot 10^{-3}$
	<i>Livermore</i>	$48. \pm 1.$	$(1.11 \pm 0.03) \cdot 10^{-3}$

Table 11: Execution time per event calculated with incident electrons, with energy 1 and 10 keV, in a water phantom, for the Geant4–DNA track structure and Geant4 condensed history EM physics studied in this work. Results obtained with Geant4 11.1.

1187 *Opt2*, with $\sim 60\%$ longer execution time, with *Geant4-DNA-Opt6* maintaining a similar ratio
 1188 with *Geant4-DNA-Opt2* at both 10 keV and 1 keV cases.

1189 When considering a 10 keV electron beam, the Geant4 EM condensed history physics
 1190 constructors have execution times $\sim 10^3 \times$ faster than the Geant4–DNA constructors. These
 1191 large differences in execution times between the Geant4 EM condensed history approach and
 1192 Geant4–DNA constructors reflect the well–known extensive computational requirements for
 1193 track structure physics models. *Opt4*, *Livermore* and *Penelope* have similar execution times
 1194 while *Opt3* is almost twice faster.

1195 The execution times of the simulations with higher energy electron beams (between 100
 1196 keV and 10 MeV) are shown in Table 12 for the Geant4 EM constructors using the condensed
 1197 history approach. For the case of 100 keV electrons in water, *Opt3* is $\sim 3 \times$ faster than the
 1198 other three EM constructors under study, with no significant differences between the other
 1199 three constructors’ execution times. At higher electron beam energies, 1 MeV and above,
 1200 *Penelope* becomes significantly slower than *Opt4* and *Livermore*. At these higher energies,
 1201 *Opt4* and *Livermore*’s execution time ratios reduce to $\sim 2.5 \times$ and $\sim 2.1 \times$ at 1 and 10 MeV,
 1202 respectively, when compared to *Opt3*.

1203 Table 13 show the execution times per event obtained in the case of a 150 MeV proton
 1204 beam, with the different Geant4 physics lists under study and two different cuts (0.1 mm

Energy (MeV)	Model	Execution time per event (μs)	$G4EM$ Constructor
			<i>Opt3</i>
0.1	<i>Opt3</i>	$48. \pm 3.$	1.
	<i>Opt4</i>	$143. \pm 2.$	3.0 ± 0.2
	<i>Penelope</i>	$145. \pm 7.$	3.0 ± 0.2
	<i>Livermore</i>	$178. \pm 3.$	3.7 ± 0.2
1	<i>Opt3</i>	$(30. \pm 1.) \cdot 10$	1.
	<i>Opt4</i>	$(75. \pm 3.) \cdot 10$	2.5 ± 0.1
	<i>Penelope</i>	$(120. \pm 10.) \cdot 10$	3.9 ± 0.4
	<i>Livermore</i>	$(74 \pm 3) \cdot 10$	2.5 ± 0.1
10	<i>Opt3</i>	$(27. \pm 1.) \cdot 10^2$	1.
	<i>Opt4</i>	$(58. \pm 3.) \cdot 10^2$	2.2 ± 0.1
	<i>Penelope</i>	$(109. \pm 4.) \cdot 10^2$	4.1 ± 0.2
	<i>Livermore</i>	$(59. \pm 1.) \cdot 10^2$	2.2 ± 0.1

Table 12: Execution times per event obtained with the simulations modelling 0.1, 1 and 10 MeV electron beams in water. Results shown for the Geant4 condensed history EM physics constructors under study, with Geant4 11.1.

1205 and 1 m). For both cut sizes the *BIC_HP* and *BERT_HP* have very similar execution
 1206 times. *QGSP_BIC_AllHP* is characterised by significantly shorter execution times than
 1207 *QGSP_BIC_HP* and *QGSP_BERT_HP*.

1208 Comparison of execution times per event obtained with *QGSP_BIC_HP* and changing
 1209 the ion fragmentation model are shown in Table 14, for a 290 MeV/u ^{12}C ion beam in
 1210 water. The simulations with BIC and INCL have similar execution times. In the case of
 1211 the smaller 0.1 mm cut, the execution time obtained with the QMD fragmentation model is
 1212 about 40% longer than in the case of BIC and INCL. In the case of the higher cut of 1 m, the
 1213 execution time obtained with QMD is about 4 times longer than BIC and INCL. Both BIC

Cut	Geant4 physics list	Execution time per event (μs)	$Geant4$ Physics List
			<i>QGSP_BIC_HP</i>
0.1 mm	<i>QGSP_BIC_HP</i>	$(133. \pm 8) \cdot 10$	1.
	<i>QGSP_BIC_AllHP</i>	$(31. \pm 1.) \cdot 10$	0.23 ± 0.02
	<i>QGSP_BERT_HP</i>	$(131. \pm 6.) \cdot 10$	0.99 ± 0.07
1 m	<i>QGSP_BIC_HP</i>	$425. \pm 9.$	1.
	<i>QGSP_BIC_AllHP</i>	$47. \pm 2.$	0.11 ± 0.01
	<i>QGSP_BERT_HP</i>	$391. \pm 9.$	0.92 ± 0.03

Table 13: Execution times per event of the Geant4 physics lists used in this work, for a 150 MeV proton beam in a water phantom. Results obtained with Geant4 11.1.

Cut	Geant4 ion fragmentation model	Execution time per event (μs)	$\frac{\text{Geant4PhysicsList}}{\text{BIC}}$
0.1 mm	BIC	$(332. \pm 9.) \cdot 10^2$	1.
	QMD	$(469. \pm 8.) \cdot 10^2$	1.41 ± 0.05
	INCL	$(321. \pm 8.) \cdot 10^2$	0.97 ± 0.04
1 m	BIC	$(47.0 \pm 0.8) \cdot 10^2$	1.
	QMD	$(188. \pm 1.) \cdot 10^2$	4.01 ± 0.07
	INCL	$(44. \pm 2.) \cdot 10^2$	0.94 ± 0.04

Table 14: Execution times of the Geant4 ion fragmentation models, BIC, INCL and QMD, for a 290 MeV/u ^{12}C ion beam in water. Results obtained with Geant4 11.1.

1214 and QMD model the interaction of projectile and target nucleons as Gaussian wave functions.
 1215 However, the reason for the significantly longer QMD execution times is that, compared to
 1216 BIC, QMD produces wave functions for all target and projectile nucleons in the interaction,
 1217 while BIC only produce wave functions for *participating* nucleons. Additionally, QMD is
 1218 time-dependent while BIC is time-independent. The INCL model instead describes the
 1219 wave functions of the interacting nucleons as free Fermi gas in a static potential well, which
 1220 shows to be computationally similar to the BIC.

1221 VIII. Discussion of the results

1222 The results of the regression testing between Geant4 10.5 and 11.1 were analysed transpar-
1223 ently with three metrics; the Mean Relative Error (MRE), the Normalised Mean Absolute
1224 Error (NMAE) and the Maximum Difference (MD). Only the MRE results are shown in this
1225 report as the three metrics provided a consistent analysis and, therefore, interpretation of
1226 the results. Nevertheless, the reader can access the full data analysis, performed with the
1227 MRE, NMAE and MD, online (Archer³²).

1228 The following sub-sections discuss the results of the G4-Med system in terms of physics
1229 capability of Geant4.

1230 VIII.A. Geant4-DNA tests

1231 Three tests have been introduced in the G4-Med suite to perform Geant4-DNA regression
1232 testing: the *Low energy electron Dose Point Kernels*, *microdosimetry* and *chemistry* tests. In
1233 summary, the *Low energy electron Dose Point Kernels* and *microdosimetry* tests show that
1234 *Geant4-DNA-Opt2* and *Geant4-DNA-Opt4* produce slightly different results in the physical
1235 quantities under study, while more significant differences can be found when these two physics
1236 constructors are compared to *Geant4-DNA-Opt6*. Differences between Geant4-DNA physics
1237 constructors in dose-mean lineal energy tend to increase for sensitive volume sizes below 100
1238 nm and move toward the smallest differences for the 1 micron volume diameter due to the
1239 absorption of most of the sub-keV electrons within the scoring site. In general the different
1240 cross sections contained in the three different physics constructors are more likely to affect
1241 studies concerning sub-keV energies and smaller scoring volumes as it has already been shown
1242 in previous relevant studies (i.e. Kyriakou et al.⁵⁵, Lindborg et al.⁵⁷, Famulari et al.¹¹⁶).

1243 The *chemistry test* shows that the *SBS*, *IRT* and *IRT-sync* can produce different G-
1244 values, depending on the chemical species under study and considered time interval after the
1245 start of the chemical stage.

1246 More Geant4-DNA tests will be added to future versions of the G4-Med suite for regres-
1247 sion testing of physics and chemistry models and for easier comparison to other simulation
1248 data or measurements.

1249 VIII.B. Electromagnetic physics tests

1250 Three new EM physics tests have been introduced in the G4–Med benchmarking system
1251 since our first work documented in Arce et al.¹, to extend the validation of Geant4 to low
1252 dose rate brachytherapy, MV X–ray external radiotherapy and electron FLASH radiother-
1253 apy, extending the coverage of the G4–Med benchmarking system to more medical physics
1254 application scenarios.

1255 The electromagnetic physics tests of the G4–Med benchmarking system showed some
1256 significant differences between Geant4 10.5 and 11.1 in *Opt3* due to differences in the multiple
1257 scattering, documented in Section IV.A.. While *Opt3* in Geant4 11.1 provides a better
1258 description of electron backscattering (see Section IV.E.1.), it is less accurate to describe the
1259 transmission of electrons in the forward direction, when compared to *Livermore*, *Penelope*
1260 and *Opt4* (see Section IV.E.2.), which then translates in a less accurate calculation of dose
1261 (see Section IV.D.). Because of this finding, a patch of Geant4 has been released (11.2.1)
1262 where the multiple scattering parameters of *Opt3* have been reverted to those of Geant4 10.5.
1263 Thanks to this change, the electron transmission and dose calculations with *Opt3* show to
1264 improve, but our results indicate that the agreement achieved with Geant4 10.5 can't still
1265 be fully reproduced. Work is under way to understand the source of the observed behaviour.

1266 The MV X-ray radiotherapy test (Section IV.C.) shows some significant discrepancies of
1267 the Geant4 penelope EM physics constructor against experimental measurements in terms
1268 of lateral dose distribution in a water phantom. This is probably due to the Penelope
1269 Bremsstrahlung model implemented in Geant4 and requires attention.

1270 Based on our findings, it is recommended to use the EM constructor *Opt4*, which shows
1271 to be the most accurate choice among the available EM constructors.

1272 VIII.C. Hadronic physics tests

1273 Three hadronic inelastic scattering tests are currently included in the G4–Med benchmarking
1274 suite.

1275 The regression testing of the nucleus–nucleus hadronic inelastic scattering cross sections
1276 (see Section V.A.1.) shows that, while the total fragmentation cross section does not change

1277 significantly between Geant4 10.5 and 11.1 for the specific nuclear reactions under study, the
1278 cross sections of production of individual secondary fragments change (see Sections [V.A.2.](#)
1279 and [V.A.3.](#)).

1280 The 300 MeV/u ^{12}C ion charge-changing cross section test (Section [V.A.3.](#)) shows
1281 significant differences between Geant4 10.5 and 11.1 in the calculation of the fragmentation
1282 yields. Geant4 11.1 describes significantly better the B isotopes yield, with approximately
1283 20-30% improvement depending on the fragmentation model, when compared to Geant4
1284 10.5. Nevertheless, this improvement is accompanied by a worsening of the results for Be
1285 production of about 10-15%. The change in the fragmentation yields may be due to the
1286 change of de-excitation channels of the Fermi Break-Up model, nevertheless more tailored
1287 tests should be performed to confirm this hypothesis. Among the three fragmentation models
1288 under study (BIC, QMD and INCL), BIC produces overall the best agreement with the
1289 reference data.

1290 The results show that it is paramount to execute the G4-Med nuclear fragmentation
1291 tests whenever there is a new development in the hadronic physics of Geant4 to monitor
1292 closely the evolution of its physics models. In addition, more tests need to be included in the
1293 G4-Med suite to benchmark individual models (e.g. the Fermi Break-Up model), to cover
1294 a wider energy range of carbon ions of interest for hadron therapy, to include more Geant4
1295 application scenarios, e.g., accelerator-based Boron Neutron Capture Therapy and neutron
1296 radiation fields.

1297 VIII.D. Electromagnetic and hadronic physics tests

1298 Two new tests have been included in the G4-Med benchmarking suite covering two new appli-
1299 cation scenarios of interest for hadrontherapy, experimental microdosimetry (Section [VI.B.](#))
1300 and *in-vivo* PET (Section [VI.C.](#)).

1301 When considering the G4-Med tests of interest for proton therapy, the following obser-
1302 vations can be made. *QGSP_BIC_HP*, *QGSP_BIC_AllHP* and *QGSP_BERT_HP* produce the
1303 same results when calculating the track-averaged LET of a 62 MeV SOBP proton beam in
1304 water. The agreement with reference data is within 15% (*Hadrontherapy* test, Section [VI.B.](#)).

1305 The regression testing of *LowEProtonBraggBeak* (Section [VI.D.1.](#)) shows a slight im-

1306 provement in Geant4 11.1 in terms of spread of a Gaussian describing the width of the
 1307 Bragg peak, while the results of the *LightIonBraggPeak* test show that the R_{82} of protons
 1308 with energy up to 200 MeV in water improves of approximately 0.2 mm in Geant4 11.1.
 1309 These improvements are ascribed to the ICRU90 adoption to calculate the low energy pro-
 1310 ton stopping powers in water in Geant4 11.1.

1311 The *ProtonC12NeutronYield* test (Section VI.D.3.) reports that *QGSP_BIC_HP* in
 1312 Geant4 11.1 produces a higher yield of neutrons (up to 20%) with energy below 10 MeV
 1313 for protons with 113 and 256 MeV energies, incident on a Fe target. No difference between
 1314 Geant4 10.5 and 11.1 is found for the lighter targets considered (C and Al) in the irradiation
 1315 scenarios under study.

1316 When considering the G4–Med tests of interest for heavy ion therapy, the *in-vivo* PET
 1317 test (Section VI.C.) shows that BIC and QMD are more adequate than INCL to describe the
 1318 positron yield for incident ^{12}C and ^{16}O beams in the targets under study (gelatin, PMMA
 1319 and polyethylene). Overall, BIC provides better description of the positron yields in the
 1320 Bragg Peak region, while QMD outperforms BIC after the distal edge of the Bragg Peak.

1321 The regression testing of the *LightIonBraggPeak* test show that the R_{82} in water changes
 1322 between Geant4 10.5 and 11.1 due to the introduction of the Lindhard Sorensen ion model,
 1323 available in Geant4 since version 11.0. When compared to Geant4 10.5, Geant4 11.1 produces
 1324 R_{82} closer to the reference data for ^{12}C ions with energies up to 250 MeV/u. For higher
 1325 energies, Geant4 10.5 tends to underestimate while Geant4 11.1 to overestimate the position
 1326 of the Bragg Peak. In the case of 400 MeV/u ^{12}C ions, the difference in the calculation of
 1327 R_{82} between Geant4 simulation results and experimental data is about 1 mm.

1328 The *ProtonC12NeutronYield* test did not report any change in the neutron production
 1329 yield of 290 MeV/u ^{12}C ions in water between Geant4 10.5 and 11.1.

1330 The 400 MeV/u ^{12}C fragmentation test in water shows a higher production of the boron
 1331 fragment, leading to a better agreement with the reference data. This result is consistent
 1332 with the results of the 300 MeV/u ^{12}C ion charge–changing cross section test (Section V.A.3.).

Arce et al.¹ recommended for hadrontherapy simulations the use of *QGSP_BIC_HP*
 with *Opt4* (identified also as *QGSP_BIC_HP_EMZ*) to describe the EM physics component, as this physics list provides an overall adequate des-

–Medtestsdocumentedinthispaper.

1333 To note, for nuclear fragmentation, a novel QMD model (Sato et al. ¹¹⁷) has been intro-
1334 duced in Geant4 11.2, called LiQMD, whose model parameters have been improved for carbon
1335 ion therapy. This model will be included in the next future in the G4–Med benchmarking ac-
1336 tivity as first results showed a better agreement with experimental reference data for nuclear
1337 fragmentation (Sato et al. ¹¹⁷).

1338 It should be noted that the provided recommendations in terms of Geant4 physics list do
1339 have some limitations. Only few physical quantities (position and spread of the Bragg Peak,
1340 neutron yields and fragment yields) in specific irradiation scenarios have been considered.
1341 Despite our effort to increase the number of hadronic physics tests (two new tests have been
1342 included since Arce et al. ¹) more tests should be added, to extend the benchmark further for
1343 nuclear fragmentation and to test neutron production and interactions.

1344 The hadronic physics of Geant4 is an active domain of development and the results of
1345 the G4–Med benchmarking system highlight the need to perform regression testing whenever
1346 there is a change in the hadronic physics of Geant4 to monitor the evolution of this Monte
1347 Carlo simulation code.

1348 VIII.D.1. Execution times test

1349 Differences in physics models (e.g. analytical or based on data), parameters and data extrap-
1350 olation techniques have an impact on simulation execution times. Therefore, a test has been
1351 added to the G4–Med benchmarking suite to compare different Geant4 EM physics construc-
1352 tors and physics lists in terms of execution times, in a very simple simulation configuration.

1353 In summary, the results show that, in general, Geant4-DNA-Opt6 is the fastest when
1354 compared to Geant4-DNA-Opt2 and Geant4-DNA-Opt4. When considering Geant4 EM con-
1355 densed history approach models under study, in the case of electron beams incident in water
1356 with energy from 100 keV to 10 MeV, Opt3 showed globally to be the fastest Geant4 EM
1357 constructor under study, followed by Opt4 and Livermore and, finally, by Penelope.

1358 The benchmarking of the execution times of the test with a 150 MeV proton beam in
1359 water, of interest for proton therapy, shows that QGSP_BIC_AllHP is the fastest Geant4
1360 physics list for proton therapy and that QGSP_BIC_HP and QGSP_BERT_HP have similar

1361 *execution times in the specific test under study. In the case of an incident 290 MeV/u ^{12}C*
1362 *ion beam, BIC and INCL ion fragmentation models shows similar execution times, while the*
1363 *QMD is significantly slower.*

1364 IX. Conclusions

1365 *The G4-Med benchmarking suite was born in 2014 from the effort of an international collabo-*
1366 *ration, the Geant4 Medical Simulation Benchmarking Group, to validate Geant4 and monitor*
1367 *its evolution for bio-medical applications. The G4-Med system was first documented in Arce*
1368 *et al.¹, where the results of the tests were reported for Geant4 10.5. In this paper, we report*
1369 *the evolution of the project in terms of novel tests included in the G4-Med testing system*
1370 *and the results of the regression testing between Geant4 10.5 and 11.1.*

1371 *In summary, new tests have been included to benchmark Geant4-DNA physics models*
1372 *and the capability of Geant4 for external X-ray and electron FLASH radiotherapy. New*
1373 *hadron therapy tests include Geant4 applications in experimental microdosimetry and in-*
1374 *vivo PET.*

1375 *Overall, the regression testing results showed the importance of the G4-Med benchmark-*
1376 *ing system to maintain and improve Geant4 for bio-medical physics applications. For ex-*
1377 *ample, thanks to this project, it was possible to identify problems in the implementation of*
1378 *the multiple scattering of the Geant4 EM constructor Opt3 in Geant4 11.1. It was then*
1379 *possible to check the impact of novel proton and ion ionisations models in results of interest*
1380 *for hadron therapy and to monitor the evolution of hadronic inelastic cross sections.*

1381 *The Mean Relative Error (MRE), the Normalised Mean Absolute Error (NMAE) and*
1382 *the Maximum Difference (MD), which could be applied transparently to any tested physical*
1383 *quantity of the G4-Med testing suite, proved to be adequate metrics for the regression testing*
1384 *and they provided a consistent analysis of the results.*

1385 *The regression testing study showed that there can be significant differences between*
1386 *different Geant4 versions, therefore it is recommended to perform in-house regression testing*
1387 *for the specific application scenario of interest, when moving from an older to a more recent*
1388 *version of Geant4.*

1389 *For the first time we reported a comparison of the Geant4 EM physics constructors and*
1390 *physics lists under study in terms of computational times. A simple Geant4 simulation was*
1391 *developed for this purpose, which will be executed for future Geant4 releases.*

1392 *The following areas of future development of the G4-Med benchmarking system arose*
1393 *from this work. While the execution of the tests in geant-val is automatised, the code main-*
1394 *tenance, the inclusion of the results in the geant-val web interface and the analysis of the*
1395 *results are manual. In order to speed-up the G4-Med system and be able to use it more*
1396 *efficiently to monitor the evolution of the Geant4 physics lists frequently (e.g. three/four*
1397 *times per year), the entire G4-Med system needs to be automatised, from the execution of*
1398 *the individual tests to the analysis of the regression testing results in terms of MRE, NMAE*
1399 *and MD. This development would allow to monitor more efficiently the evolution of Geant4*
1400 *and to perform swiftly regression testing studies few times per year before the public release*
1401 *of Geant4, while now, provided our current resources and the status of the developed software*
1402 *tools used in the project, we are able to perform regression testing only with public releases*
1403 *of Geant4 (in other words, one Geant4 release per year). An extensive effort is under way*
1404 *to achieve this goal.*

1405 *The regression testing showed that the hadronic physics component of Geant4 can change*
1406 *significantly from a Geant4 release to the next one and needs particular attention. Provided*
1407 *the complexity of this physics component, there is a need to extend the G4-Med system to a*
1408 *wider set of tests dedicated to fundamental physics quantities (e.g. hadronic cross sections*
1409 *and final states of individual interactions). In addition, more tests should be included in the*
1410 *G4-Med benchmarking system, especially for radioactivity, nuclear medicine and neutron*
1411 *production and interactions.*

1412 X. Acknowledgements

1413 *J. Archer and C. White were financially supported by the Australian Government Re-*
1414 *search Training Program Scholarship. Z. Li's PhD at University of Bordeaux, France,*
1415 *was financially supported by China Scholarship Council, through a four-year funding (No*
1416 *201906680103), in collaboration with Fudan University, Shanghai. LP2I Bordeaux also*
1417 *thanks CNRS/IN2P3 for providing support to the Geant4 project (<http://geant4.in2p3.fr>).*

1418 *M. A. Cortés-Giraldo and J. M. Quesada were financially supported by Grant PID2021-*
1419 *123879OB-C21 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by “ERDF A way of*
1420 *making Europe”. S. Guatelli and A. Rosenfeld acknowledge the financial support of the*
1421 *NHMRC Idea grant ID2028435 and ARC Discovery Project DP230103091.*

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